

Building a Sustainable Joint between Rural and Urban Areas through Circular and Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains

D2.1

Recommendations of zero-waste in wood-based products

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Authors

Sirje Vares
Margareta Wahlström
Petr Hradil
Terttu Vainio
Petri Jetsu
Robert Henderson
Markku Nikkilä
Ugutz Arrizabalaga
Arne Schirp

Organisations

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
ETC Solutions
Elastopoli
Garnica
WKI Fraunhofer Wilhelm-Klauditz-Institut

Approved by

Javier García Jaca (Tecnalia)

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Executive summary

Construction wastes are the valuable stock of resources that can be utilized, but for now, those are underexploited and thus, causing costs for society and environmental burdens. Main wooden waste utilization case is the incineration, but for boosting material-based utilisation, new wooden based product innovations should be needed.

The study assessing current situation of using wood-based construction materials and their environmental performance (GWP) but also future possibilities for reuse and recycling wooden waste. The goal for innovative BASAJAUN bio-based product development and design is to use recycled wood (foam formed insulation, foam formed wood plastic composite, thermoplastic composites, and structural panels). Quality of the recycled wood but also waste prevention and reduction is studied. This report includes following chapters for:

- sustainability and circularity measures (Chapter 2),
- international initiatives and requirements related to the waste, resources and sustainability (Chapter 3),
- wooden material production phase and their environmental performance (GWP) (Chapter 4),
- management and quality of recovered wood, waste prevention and reduction issues (Chapter 5)
- annual construction and demolition waste streams; caused GWP and reset carbon storage in case of incineration (Chapter 6),
- BASAJAUN product development for waste prevention, GWP (Chapter 7)
- barriers, which should be overcome for reuse and recycling of wooden waste (Chapter 8),
- good practices: material passports and design for waste reduction (Chapter 9),
- discussions and recommendations (Chapter 10).

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Glossary

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Full term</i>
CDW	Construction Demolition Waste
CLT	Cross-laminated timber
CO ₂ e	Carbon dioxide equivalent
COM	COM
CPR	Construction Products Regulation
DfD/A	Design for disassembly and adaptability
EC	European Council
EoW	End of Waste
EU	European Union
EPD	Environmental product declaration
EWC	European Waste Codes
GPP	Green Public Procurement
GWP	Global warming potential
HM	Heavy Metals
IPCC	The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCM	Product Lifecycle Management
LoW	List of Waste
LVL	Laminated Veneer Lumber
mdf-board	Medium-density fibreboard
OH	Organic Halogens
OSB	Oriented Strand Board
SVHC	Substances of Very High Concern
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WPC	Wood Plastic Composite

Definitions

Post-consumer wood: waste originating from final wood products whose life cycle ended (i.e. which are unsuitable for further use, worn out or withdrawn from use) and which were used as final products at least during their first useful life.

Wood by-products: waste originating from the wood sector, i.e. from manufacturing where wood and its derivatives are comprehensively processed; wood by-products are generated at the subsequent stages of wood processing into wood materials and final wood products.

Recycling: a recovery process in which waste is reprocessed into products, materials or substances used for their original purpose or other purposes; this includes reprocessing of organic material (organic recycling), but excludes energy recovery and reprocessing into materials which will be used as fuels or for filling excavations.

Zero waste approach (waste neutrality): When waste production (sources) and –consumption (sinks) are equal, then total net waste is zero. This could be achieved through reuse and recycling.

Allocation: partitioning the input or output flows of a process to the product system under study

Life cycle assessment (LCA): compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle

1 Introduction

This report studies circular economy approach and zero-waste strategy for wood-based construction. There is a different possibility to move towards zero-waste in wooden material production with better/efficient wooden material utilization from forest to the product production but also utilization of waste generated during building construction and beyond the building life cycle.

High importance should be given for the responsibly in wood material sourcing and manufacturing processes, creating high quality products, which are safe to produce and use, which are long lasting and made from natural and renewable materials.

Wood, which purchased from sustainable managed forest, and used in construction sector provides a long-term carbon storage. Buildings with wood shows often lower carbon footprint and with a significant increase in wood construction, it is possible to move towards carbon-neutral construction.

EU has set a target for recycling 70% of construction and demolition waste by 2020 [3]. This overall target could be reached by recycling of concrete elements by downgrading them into aggregates. However, wooden based materials are utilized mainly for the energy production, but according to the waste hierarchy and utilization priority, waste substance should be utilized as a material, rather than for energy. Reuse and recycling of wooden material is still rare and only few examples are available.

Longevity and a sustainable use of resources is a key issue for the new material and product development. BASAJAUN project targets the development of new innovative products from recycled wood and finally their use in demo buildings.

This resulting to the fact, that wooden material life and carbon storage duration is extended from the second material transformation, use of virgin materials and waste generation is avoided, and finally new bio-based materials allows to use more wood, instead of carbon-intensive construction materials. All those beneficiaries promote reaching low carbon construction target, which is set for the European construction sector.

The premise is that wooden C&D waste is possible to recycle into the new BASAJAUN products, the products will show lower carbon impacts compared to the currently used products with the same function, and after end of life, those products transformed also to the next products by cascading the use of wood. This will be dealt in next BASAJAUN project reports:

- Technologies for wood recycling and recovery- D2.2
- LCA assessment for BASAJAUN materials and components - D2.4
- End of life, recyclability and reusability - D2.5

Main goal of this report is to show holistic view of the impact of wooden materials recyclability – moving towards zero waste approach, fulfilling circular economy targets for waste reduction and thus improving environmental performance of buildings.

However, reuse/recycle of materials from already built constructions differs significantly from the future constructed buildings when 'design for deconstruction' is a norm and for the case when material and products developed for their next transformations.

2 Background

2.1 Sustainability

United Nation defined sustainable development in their report 'Our common future' already in 1987 [4] and according to that, sustainable development is a development that "meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

In 2005, World Summit on Social Development identified sustainable development goals for the economic development, social development and environmental protection. Thus, economy, environment and society are forming three pillars for the sustainability.

Construction sector is highly important on the sustainable development as it causes substantial impacts on the all those three pillars:

- it absorbs considerable amount of resources, which have consequential impacts on economic, social conditions and environment;
- it represents a significant share of the economic asset of individuals, organisations and nations;
- it is a key sector in national economies;
- it providing value and employment;
- it has impact to poverty reduction, through the social services provided by the built environment.

Sustainability is measured through sustainability indicators and thus indicators are set separately for the assessment of environmental-, social- and economic performance of buildings. ISO 21929 [5] provides guidelines to develop new sustainability indicators for the buildings. According to the IPCC, sustainability is a dynamic process; indicators helping set sustainability targets, monitor the developments and follow the processes.

Sustainability assessment supporting industries to evaluate their existing systems, technologies and products but also enables to show improvements through the development of new sustainable solutions. Product Lifecycle Management (LCM) is the most effective way for managing a company's products all across their lifecycles, from the very first product idea to the way until it is retired and disposed [6].

Sustainability in Construction sector covers many aspects throughout the whole construction value chain and across the life cycle. It is a valuable measure for different actors and level:

- investors and owners of real estate;
- occupiers and users of buildings;
- planners, developers and designers;
- **manufacturers of products;**
- contractors;
- facility managers and real estate agents;
- public bodies (housing, building, traffic, environment).

CEN/TC 350 working group worked out a set of standards for the Sustainability assessment of Construction work. The standards give general principles for the assessment in framework level and more specific assessment guidance in building and product level.

General Framework level standard gives principles, requirements and guidelines for the sustainability assessment of buildings [7]. In addition, there are framework standards for the assessment of environmental, social- and economic performance [8], [9], [10]. Standards that are more specific are available for the assessment of environmental, economic, and social performance of buildings [11], [12], [13]. For the product level assessment Environmental product declaration, Communication format B to B and Methodology for selection and use of generic data standard are available [11], [14], [15].

2.2 Circular Economy

Circular economy goal is to eliminate wastes and make possible continual use of resources. With the high material consumption and insufficient availability of our natural resources. Circular economy gained recently high importance instead of the linear economy, which bases on the common procedure - produce, use and dispose. In circular economy, the goal is to keep materials and products as long as possible in the life cycle. There are various approaches to 'circular' business and economic models, which all tackle with the waste utilization. Some of them are listed below:

- using a waste as a resource for other product ('Blue economy'),
- a strategy of waste prevention by extension a product life cycle from cradle to cradle ('Cradle to cradle approach'),
- creating closed-loop processes, in which waste is seen as input and thus eliminating undesirable by-product ('Industrial ecology'),
- resource recovery from wastes for reducing need for landfill and extracting maximum value from wastes ('Resource recovery').

According to European Commission:

Circular economy aims to maintain the value of products, materials and resources for as long as possible by returning them into the product cycle at the end of their use, while minimising the generation of waste. The fewer products we discard, the less materials we extract, the better for our environment.

According to Ellen MacArthur:

A circular economy is based on the principles of designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use, and regenerating natural systems.

For taking benefits from Circular economy, materials and products should be designed out of waste and pollution. VDI (German engineers association) worked out general guideline for the recycling-oriented product developments [16]. The guide points out the designer's role, who defines properties in the course of the product development process. Thus, design for circularity (for reuse and recycle)

should be integrated into the product development process from the start. In addition to the process guides, the document gives also some practical product examples but unfortunately, none of them related to the construction materials and wooden products. However, presented product development processes and recycling criteria's are general and valid for all kind of products.

2.3 Life Cycle Assessment

Quantified evaluation of the environmental performance of industrial products, systems and buildings is based on the Life Cycle assessment (LCA) method. Life cycle is a 'cradle to grave' system approach.

For the product design, it identifies opportunities to improve environmental performance of products at various points of their lifetime. It assists informing decision makers, governmental or other bodies in strategic planning and priority setting, weather to concentrate to the product, process design or redesign. The assessment gives base for environmental claims or marketing.

LCA is standardised method, where international standards, ISO 14040 [17] and 14044 [18], providing main principles and frameworks, specifying requirements and giving guidelines for the assessment. European standard EN 15978 [11] is developed for the assessment of environmental performance of buildings. This standard gives specific calculation rules for the assessment of the environmental performance of new and existing buildings.

For the assessment of buildings, LCA covers the whole building life cycle and based on data obtained on Environmental Product Declarations (EPD), their information modules (Figure 1) and all other necessary data for the calculation. Core rules for the life cycle assessment and for compiling product based EPDs are given in the new amendment of EN 15804 [19].

Figure 1 Building life cycle modulus [19]

LCA aims assessing also environmental benefits and loads resulting from the reusable products, recyclable materials and useful energy carriers, leaving the system as a secondary materials or fuel. In such a way, the assessment widens also beyond the building life cycle (Phase D).

LCA method provides different indicators for the assessment of buildings, products and materials. Resulting indicators are those describing environmental impacts, resource use and waste generation but also future output flows, which assessing material amounts for the reuse, recycling, recovery for energy.

2.4 Zero waste concept

Zero waste is defined as equilibrium between generated and utilized waste throughout the building lifecycle. The net amount of waste M_w should be zero (or below zero, if we are talking about waste negative building). It can be expressed as

$$M_w = M_{out} - M_{in} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The generated M_{out} waste includes any production waste that does not become by-product [2] and any other waste (e.g. for disposal or energy production) that is not recovered for reuse or recycling. The utilized waste M_{in} is any waste used in production or maintenance of the building excluding the waste recovered as product (through the end-of-waste process).

The general strategy is to decrease M_{out} as much as possible but the possibility to increase M_{in} by utilizing waste from other sources than buildings (with the adequate environmental permits) create opportunities to reach zero or even negative balance.

It should be noted that there is a clear relation between the waste and carbon footprint reduction. Any material that is not becoming waste, is recovered from waste, or is utilized as waste in new production substitutes the virgin material otherwise used in its place. The production of virgin material is almost always more carbon intensive than recycling and reuse.

2.5 Wooden construction materials

Wood is consumed by various sectors, but one most wooden raw material demanding sector is construction. Harvested logs are sawmilled and processed further and thus logs are the source for different building products. Typical wood products for construction is a timber, different structural laminated wood products (Glulam, LVL, CLT) but also wood-based boards and panels (plywood, chipboard, fibreboard, OSB).

Wood resource plays an essential role in the circular economy because it is renewable, recyclable, reusable and biodegradable. However, in the environmental, economic and social point of view it is important how optimal the forest management and sawing is done. How the selection of logs and wood edging is done by combining the diameter, length, and properties with respect to the appropriate processes and product's needs. Especially, choosing the right log for the products will maximize the desired product yield and thus saves our natural wood recourse.

Wood Wisdom project '€CO2' (2010 - 2013), defined typical model of wood-based product life cycle. This is shown in Figure 2 [20].

Figure 2 System boundaries for the LCA of wooden products 'cradle to gate' [20]

Life cycle assessment method is a tool for calculating environmental and economic impacts from product production, use, and end of life treatment. Environmental product declarations (EPD) gives a quantified environmental impact results for the products. Global Warming Potential (GWP) is one of the most used impact categories. It reflects relatively well also energy- and raw-material efficiency. Current GWP impacts of different wooden material production is shown in the report chapter 4.1.

2.6 Wooden materials and their Specific properties

For the quantification of environmental impacts of assessed products and buildings general methodological issues are dealt in Environmental product declarations standard [19] but also in ILCD handbook [21], EC Level(s) assessment methodology [22] and various complementary national methods [23]. In addition to those, different certification systems for sustainable buildings give credits from using renewable resources and recycled materials. Definition of the methods and standards, for calculating impacts from wooden material, product and construction, will be evaluated more thoroughly in the BASAJAUN report D2.3 [24] (not written in time being).

Wooden material and products have many specific sustainability related benefits compared to the other building materials. Wooden products are made from the renewable resources and thus, using wood saving our limited fossil-based-resources, and in some cases also decreasing otherwise used mineral resources. Wood sequester carbon dioxide from atmosphere and this benefit could be taken into account as CO₂-removal in GWP calculations.

There are many methodological key questions how to consider these benefits in sustainability assessments:

- inclusion of biogenic carbon,
- counting benefits and load from recycling,
- caused changes in land use,
- delayed emissions (stored carbon),
- impact allocation to the by-products.
- inherent energy content, etc.

The methodology for the specific questions is discussed more thoroughly in a sector or product based category rules documents. CEN/TC 175 working group, "Round and sawn timber", worked out product category rules for the round and sawn timber use in construction sector [25]. Category rule documents ensuring that EPDs, which following this standard, providing quantified environmental information on a harmonized and scientific basis.

Biogenic carbon content and sequestered carbon dioxide

In the tree growth and photosynthesis process, tree absorbs (sequester) carbon dioxide from atmosphere and releases oxygen back into the atmosphere. Depending on tree species, growth comprises varying amounts of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and extractives. From that, it is determined that average carbon content of wood is close to 50% and this average value is widely proposed for use [26], [27], [28].

Carbon content of wood is often converted to the sequestered carbon dioxide amount. Calculation of sequestered carbon dioxide amount based on biogenic carbon content and the volume of wood, density and moisture content and it can be expressed according to following equation [27]:

$$P_{CO_2} = \frac{44}{12} \times cf \times \frac{\rho_w \times V_w}{1 + \frac{\omega}{100}} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- Value 44 is atomic weight of carbon dioxide and 12 is atomic weight of carbon (the ratio of CO₂ to carbon weight is 44/12= 3.67).
- cf is the carbon content of woody biomass (0.5 is a default value)
- ω moisture content of the product (e.g.12%)
- ρ_w density of woody biomass of the product at that moisture content (kg/m³);
- V_w is the volume of the solid wood product at that moisture content (m³).

Carbon storage

Wooden based materials have their inherent property to store carbon during the wooden mass growth. In line with EN 15804 and life cycle modularity calculations, carbon storage could be taken into account as input value and release as an output value. Carbon storage is considered as a part of the global warming potential in EPDs [19].

For the carbon storage calculation, oven-dry mass of wood entering or leaving a product system is multiplied by the carbon storage value. Characterization factor for carbon storage is either 'minus 1' or 'plus 1' and it depends on the forest managements systems from where the wood material is obtained to the product production.

From sustainable managed forest, carbon neutrality can be assumed, i.e. biogenic carbon balance over a product life cycle is 0. Carbon fluxes are taken into account when wood entering to the process (life cycle phase A1) as negative value, and positive value (phase C3) when wood product leaving the Life Cycle. Leaving the system could be happen through the energy utilization or through the next reuse- or material recycling case.

Greenhouse gas impact and carbon storage examples are shown in Figure 3 for the wooden and concrete building cases when wood obtained from sustainable managed forests (life cycle stages A1-4) [29].

Figure 3 GHG (kg as CO₂e) and carbon content (as carbon storage, kg CO₂) from wooden- and concrete multi-storey building materials for the life cycle stages A1-4 [29]

Note: A-E are wooden buildings, with different wooden structures, F is a concrete building

In case when the forest management is not known or wood is obtained from non-sustainable managed forest, this carbon storage benefit cannot be applied. However, when subsequent product system receiving recycled wood, carbon biogenic carbon content can be considered.

Figure 4 gives an example from the assessment of global warming potentials for the CLT based floor slab for the case where carbon neutrality can be considered [30]. According to this result, it is seen that total life cycle impact is 27.5 kg CO₂e/m², when in production stage, with carbon storage, it was -65.2 kg CO₂e/m².

Figure 4 GWP for the Life Cycle of CLT based floor slab [30].

Allocation

Manufacturing of wooden products resulting to the main product but also different by-products and wastes, depending on the process, efficiency and yield.

Life cycle assessment result depending on the chosen system borders as well as the allocation of environmental loads and benefits to the different products created in the same process. Those intermediate or even discarded products can be recycled to become inputs for other processes.

EN 15804 [19] says that when dealing with systems involving multiple products and recycling processes, allocation should be avoided as far as possible by dividing the unit process into different sub-processes. However, avoiding allocation is often not possible as separation of process production flows between main product and other by- or co-products.

There are many different possibilities for allocation like natural causality relationship, economic allocation or some other physical parameter.

In any case, allocation shall respect the main purpose of the processes studied, allocating all relevant products and functions appropriately. Before allocation, it is good to determine co-products, by-products and wastes:

- By-products are utilized, but they are least economically valuable and secondary to maintain main product production;
- Co-products are of equal value and primary to maintain main product production;
- Waste has no economic value or has a negative value and not recovered.

EN 15804 [19] appoints that flows, leaving the system at the end-of-waste boundary of the product stage (A1-A3) shall be allocated as by-products.

Jointly produced co-products shall be allocated as follows:

- allocation shall be based on physical properties when the difference between revenue is low,
- in all other cases allocation shall be based on economic value
- material flow carrying inherent property like energy content, stored biogenic carbon shall always be allocated reflected the physical flow.

The impact of allocation method to the impact categories is studied by Linkosalmi et al (2020) for timber products [31]. Results indicate that allocation influences how impacts are distributed to the sawmilling products. Sawn timber as main product is getting biggest impact in all cases, because of the biggest quantity in production.

According to the results, economic allocation gives more realistic impacts to the by-products with low value. Subdivision with Economic allocation was most holistic option, because of impacts are allocated by processes, volumes and values.

Table 1 Impact distribution from stages A1-3 with different allocation factors [31]

	Factor 1 (%)	Factor 2 (%)	Factor 3 (%)	Factor 4 (%)	Reference (%)
Sawn timber	45.81	59.10	49.96	60.97	63.87
Chips	30.22	23.46	28.36	22.25	20.15
Sawn dust	13.04	9.79	12.37	9.32	8.70
Bark	8.59	5.98	5.83	5.73	5.72
Cutter shavings	2.34	1.68	3.49	1.72	1.56
Sum	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Figure 5 GWP result of sawn timber (A1-3) according to different allocation factors [31]

In environmental product declaration of timber products mostly economic allocation has been used, however there is a critic also about this as the market prices can vary depend on time and location [32]. It is shown that implementing different allocation rules in LCA assessment the result will be different.

Inherent energy

Energy is dealt in Life Cycle Assessment as a resource and shall include in each module declared in EPD. Parameter describing energy resource use are renewable- and non-renewable primary energy but also renewable and non-renewable primary energy resource, used as a raw material. Energy resources reported in MJ according to their net calorific value.

It is essential for the outcome of the energy assessment, whether the energy estimate includes the also the product's own calorific value. This is important for the products, materials and raw materials that can also be used as a fuels, such as wood based materials are.

2.7 Wooden waste through the building life cycle

The construction sector represents one of the biggest sources of waste in terms of volume with approximately 70.5 million tons of wood waste generated annually and. around one third of waste wood is recycled (Source: WoodCircus project, <https://woodcircus.eu/index.php/about/>).

Whereas BASAJAN project estimates that potential utilizable post-consumer wood waste in European Union may be at the level of almost 53 million m³ and generated wood by-products at the level of approximately 104.0-113.4 million m³ (BASAJAUN D1.3) [33]

For the efficient use of our natural resource 'wood', the target for construction sector should be the zero-waste approach. This is assumed to be possible through the utilization of by-products, wooden construction and demolition wastes, but also utilizing post-consumer waste wood for the production of new innovative wooden materials. However, hazardous and contaminated substances should be removed first from the loop. Wooden material waste generation during the life cycle of buildings is presented in Figure 6.

Zero waste approach: total net from produced waste and consumed waste is 0.

Figure 6 Wooden waste generation during building life cycle and waste source

3 Initiatives related to the waste and resources

Key conclusions/message

- EU legislation contains several initiatives to boost circular economy solutions in the construction sector through waste prevention, reuse and recycling. E.g for the revision of the Construction Products Regulation it is proposed to introduce recycled content requirements for certain construction products, taking into account their safety and functionality
- Waste recycling to be seen as part of sustainability of construction
- Several legislative actions taken for increasing recycling of construction and demolition waste into new products (in Waste Framework Directive a mandatory recovery target of 70 % to be reached in 2020 and under evaluation potential material specific targets in 2024)
- End-of-waste concept provides a possibility to change the waste status to product status - EoW concept is an interesting option to be further investigated for BASAJUAN products developed
- Possibilities for CE-marking to be further checked for BASAJUAN products

3.1 Waste Framework directive

The policy process related to the wastes emphasises to the waste prevention, reuse and material recycling. The Waste Framework Directive [2] is one of the cornerstone pieces of the Community legislation on waste. EC set already in 2006 [34] priorities for the waste management, so called waste hierarchy. According to that, privilege should be given for material utilization (reuse, recycle) rather than energy utilization (Figure 7). However, for wood waste energy utilization is so far more common than reuse and recycle.

Figure 7 Waste management hierarchy [34]

Concepts for waste managements are described in EU Directive 2008/98/EC [2] and its amending Directive on waste 2018/851/EC [3]. In which, Annex II gives a guidance for waste recovery. Waste

recovery is important also in context of BASAJAUN project especially because of the intention to use recycle wood in the development of new innovative bio-based products.

According to the directive, **waste** defined as a substance, which the holder discards. **Waste management** includes the collection, transport, recovery (including sorting), and disposal of waste. According to LCA approach (EN 15804); those processes should be taken into account in the product life cycle stages C2-4.

The directive defines also recovery and waste utilization as follows:

- **Recovery of waste:** any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function, in the plant or in the wider economy
- **Preparing for re-use:** checking, cleaning or repairing recovery operations, by which products or components of products that have become waste are prepared so that they can be re-used without any other pre-processing.
- **Reuse of waste** includes any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials, which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function, in the plant or in the wider economy.
- **Reuse of waste:** any operation by which products or components that are not waste are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived.
- **Recycling of waste:** any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations.

The Waste Framework Directive (WFD) (2008/98 / EC, update 2018/851) [3], sets a mandatory material recovery target of 70 % for non-hazardous construction by 2020. Additionally, the Commission shall consider material-type specific recycling targets for construction waste by 2024.

The Waste Framework Directive (WFD) 2008/98/EC includes the option to set so called end-of-waste (EoW) criteria under which specified waste fractions shall cease to be waste. If these criteria are fulfilled, the material will no longer be classified as a waste, but it will instead become a product subject to free trade and use (although for specific purposes). Article 6 of the WFD regulates the circumstances under which certain specified types of waste cease to be waste. This “end-of-waste” status is reached when the waste has undergone a recovery operation, including recycling, and complies with specific criteria to be developed in accordance with the following cumulative conditions:

- a) the substance or object has a specific application;
- b) a market or demand exists for such a substance or object;
- c) the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing legislation and standards applicable to products; and
- d) the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.

Article 6(4) of the WFD provides that where no EoW criteria have been set at EU level, “Member States may decide case by case whether certain waste has ceased to be waste taking into account the applicable case law”. One of the benefits in this approach is that national differences can be considered. However, it is important to note that when a waste reaches national end of waste status it only ceases to be waste in that member state. The waste is still to be considered as a waste in other member states and the regulation on shipments of waste is still applicable to it. Member states shall notify the Commission of decisions of national EoW criteria for a specific waste cease to be a waste.

When classified as a waste, environmental and health protection aspects of the use of CDW for construction purposes are regulated by national (and EU) waste legislation. If a CDW aggregate obtains EoW status and ceases to be waste it becomes a product. In that case the use of the material will be regulated entirely by legislation on products. However, when the CDW derived aggregate is used as construction material in applications for which harmonised product standards have been developed, the Construction Products Regulation, CPR (305/2011/EU) applies regardless of the EoW status [38][39].

The European Commission has already set down end-of-waste criteria for iron, steel and aluminium scrap [40], glass cullet [41] and copper scrap [42] and criteria for various other materials (paper waste, biodegradable waste (compost/digestate) potentially integrated in Fertilizers Regulation, waste plastics) are under preparation.

Figure 8 Options for End-of-waste concepts

End of waste status has an effect on the calculation of environmental impacts (see allocation, Chapter 2.5). The material recovery target concerns only non-hazardous waste. The classification of waste as non-hazardous or hazardous is also regulated in the WFD [3], with reference to Annex III of WFD [35] (Annex III was revised 2014) and the European List of Waste [37] (LoW; revised 2014). The EWC divides wastes into 20 categories according to their origin. Some wastes are automatically defined as hazardous or non-hazardous, while other wastes are marked as ‘mirror entries’, i.e. the judgement as to whether they are hazardous or non-hazardous depends on their concentration of dangerous substances or their hazard properties. If the waste is potentially hazardous or non-hazardous according to LoW, the waste status has to be assessed against the criteria for all hazard properties presented in the revised Annex III of the WFD. For example, a waste containing hazardous substances (such as a specific metal oxide) is classified as hazardous if the concentration of the hazardous

substance(s) exceeds a given concentration limit. The waste classification process requires detailed knowledge of chemical legislation and can be rather laborious because all hazardous properties in Annex III need to be taken into account. The classification of waste as hazardous does not hinder recycling, but waste classification has several legal implications in waste management. There are numerous EU regulations setting special requirements for waste defined as hazardous waste: legal procedures in waste handling (permit, taxation, inspections), requirements on waste storage, transportation, reuse/recycling and disposal of waste (e.g. landfilling), traceability from production to final destination and ban on the mixing of hazardous waste.

3.2 Resource Efficient Europe

EU's concern has been already many years the continuity of our limited resources and their use in a sustainable way by minimising their impacts on environment. Thus, there has been many initiatives related to the resource efficiency and sustainability.

For example, The Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe (COM 2011/571) [1] proposes ways to increase resource productivity and decouple economic growth from resource use and its environmental impact. It raises the **importance of exchanging information** about resource efficiency between partners in value chains and across sectors, this can prevent waste, boost innovation and create new markets. The main idea is to **turn waste into a resource**.

Roadmap estimates, that improving the **reuse of raw materials through greater 'industrial symbiosis'** (where the waste of some firms become a resource for others), the annual savings across the EU will be 1.4 bn € and it generates sales 1.6 bn €.

EU Green Public Procurement (GPP) (COM (2008) 400) [35] are designed to make it easier for public authorities to purchase goods, services and works with reduced environmental impacts. The use of the criteria is voluntary and not all criteria are valid for all cases.

Figure 9 Green Public Procurement icon

Currently (2020) several GPP Criteria is set for the products but many in a revision stage or under development work¹. Following GPP are interesting in the point of view BASAJAUN project:

¹ https://susproc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/product_bureau/projects.html

- building sector
 - GPP Criteria is set in 2016 for the office buildings [43] ,
- building product industry
 - GPP Criteria draft is set for windows and doors, but this was put on a hold, as it did not provide sufficient environmental benefits.
 - GPP criteria for the indoor and outdoor paints and varnishes is set in 2017 [44].
 - Whereas, for wooden floor coverings, EU EcoLabel criteria is under revision.

Green Public procurement report [43] shows an example of Criteria, which related to the resource efficient construction for the Office Buildings.

Table 2 GPP Criteria for Resource efficient construction, case office building [43]

Resource efficient construction	
Life cycle performance	
Performance of the main building elements	- <i>Two options based on EPDs and/or LCA results</i>
Construction product recycled content	
Incorporation of recycled content	- <i>15% (Core) and 30% (Comprehensive)</i>
Wood sourcing	
Legal sourcing of wood construction materials	- <i>Due diligence along the supply chain</i>
Waste management plans	
Demolition waste audit and management plan	- <i>55% (Core) and 70% (Comprehensive) by weight</i> - <i>Structure and fit-out elements</i> - <i>Hazardous waste risk assessment</i> - <i>Bill of quantities and methods for recycling and re-use</i> - <i>On-site monitoring and accounting</i>
Site waste management plan	- <i>11 tonnes (Core) and 7 tonnes (Comprehensive) per 100 m² floor area</i>

According to the resource efficient Europe, higher priority need be given to the reuse and recycling. The requisites, for turning wastes into resources, are:

- life cycle approach should be integrated into product design,
- better collection processes should be developed,
- incentives for waste prevention and recycling should be available,
- public investments into modern facilities for waste treatment and high-quality recycling should be available.

Milestone:

By 2020, waste is managed as a resource and waste generated per capita is in absolute decline. Recycling and re-use of waste are economically attractive options for public and private actors due to widespread separate collection and the development of functional markets for secondary raw materials. Energy recovery is limited to non-recyclable materials, landfilling is virtually eliminated, and high-quality recycling is ensured.

To achieve the goals for residual waste close to zero, existing prevention, re-use, recycling, recovery need to be reviewed, end of waste criterions should to be developed for key products, minimum recycled material rates, durability and reusability criteria's need to be established. For construction

sector, it suggests promoting sustainable use of wood (Communication on the sustainable competitiveness of the construction sector, 2011, Communication on sustainable buildings, 2013)

3.3 New Circular economy action Plan

EU had so far no clear requirements to ensure that all products placed on the EU market are sustainable and stand the test of circularity. New Circular Economy Action Plan [45] was launched in 2020 which pointed out the importance of sustainability, provides future orientated agenda but also legislative initiative for the product policy, according to that it will make sustainable products, services and business models the norm and transform consumption patterns so that **no waste is produced in the first place**.

The New Circular Economy Action plan presents following measures:

- Make sustainable products the norm in the EU;
- Empower consumers and public buyers;
- Focus on the sectors that use most resources and where the potential for circularity is high such as: electronics and ICT; batteries and vehicles; packaging; plastics; textiles; construction and buildings; food; water and nutrients;
- Ensure less waste;
- Make circularity work for people, regions and cities,
- Lead global efforts on circular economy.

The New Circular Economy action plan also mentions the following sustainability principles, which are discussed in chapter 3.6 in context of Eco-design.

In the Circular Economy Action Plan, for construction and building sector, it is mentioned that the strategy for the Sustainable Built Environment includes climate, energy and resource efficiency themes, but also management of construction and demolition waste, and improving availability of digitalized information about buildings. According to the annex, key action date for Sustainable Built Environment is 2021 [45].

In the previous Circular Economy Action Plan from 2015 (EC 2015) [46], construction and demolition was mentioned as a priority area and the plan listed three actions related to C&DW required for the achievement of a circular economy. The following guidance or framework documents have been developed as a response to these actions (EC, 2019) [47]:

- Waste Management Protocol: this aims to ensure recovery of valuable resources and adequate waste management in the construction and demolition sector.
- Waste Audit Guideline: pre-demolition guidelines to boost high-value recycling as well as voluntary recycling protocols aimed at improving quality and building confidence.
- EU Level(s) – European reporting framework for sustainable buildings: this aims to facilitate the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings. (see further chapter 3.5)

Figure 10 Guidelines and protocols published by the European Commission

Notes: EU guideline for Waste audit (2017) [48], EU Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol [49] and Construction Waste Measurement Protocol published by Encord in 2013 [50] and a Framework for Level(s) in 2017 [22].

3.4 Construction Product Regulation

The main aim of the Construction Products Regulation [51] is to remove barriers to trade of construction products between member states in the European Economic Area. It makes CE-marking mandatory for most construction products sold in EU countries, which are covered by a harmonised product standard or a construction product that conforms to a European Technical Assessment, which has been issued for the product. The CPR requires that harmonised test methods are used in the performance declarations in order to remove trade barriers between member states. The CPR (as former Construction Products Directive) does not intend to harmonise existing national regulations and requirements concerning the actual construction works (e.g. national regulation for indoor air quality). Member States and public and private sector procurers are free to set their own requirements on the performance of buildings and construction works and thus performance levels of products.

The CPR replaced the former Construction Products Directive and introduced the life cycle perspective when assessing the performance of a construction product. The “life cycle” is defined “as the consecutive and interlinked stages of a construction product’s life, from raw material acquisition or generation from natural resources to final disposal” (thus meaning “from cradle to grave”).

Construction Product Regulation [51] sets seven basic requirements for the construction work where requirement 3 are given for the safety of Hygiene, health and environment and requirement 7 for the sustainable use of natural resources.

Requirement 3 - The Construction works must be designed and built in such a way that they will, throughout their life cycle, not be a threat to the hygiene or health and safety of workers, occupants or neighbours, nor have an exceedingly high impact, over their entire life cycle, on the environmental quality or on the climate during their construction, use and demolition.

Requirement 7 - The construction works must be designed, built and demolished in such a way that the use of natural resources is sustainable and in particular ensure the following:

- reuse or recyclability of the construction works, their materials and parts after demolition,
- durability of the construction works;
- use of environmentally compatible raw and secondary materials in the construction work.

The New Circular Action plan specifically mentions the need to improve sustainability performance and promote circularity of construction products is addressed in the context of the **revision of the Construction Product Regulation** (REFINED INDICATIVE OPTIONS FOR THE REVIEW OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION, VERSION 2 - 08.04.2020).

This will include introduction of recycled content requirements for certain construction products, taking into account their safety and functionality; promoting measures to improve the durability and adaptability of built assets in line with the *Circular Economy principles for buildings design* [54] and developing digital logbooks for buildings.

3.5 Sustainability in Construction sector - Level(s)

Low-carbon assessment of buildings is already required by law in the Netherlands and France. In Sweden, the assessment obligation will enter into force in 2022. The European Commission has also drawn up a proposal for a common EU approach to assessing the low-carbon and sustainable development of buildings (the so-called Levels method).

In the circular economy, the carbon footprint and environmental footprint of the materials is increasingly taken into account in material choices, e.g. European Commission's Level(s) method for measuring the resource efficiency, circular economy and ecology of construction.

'Principles for building design' [54] proposing use of Level(s) assessment [52] for the integration of life cycle assessment into public procurement, EU sustainable finance framework and exploring the appropriateness of **setting of carbon reduction targets and the potential of carbon storage**. It also proposes revision of material recovery targets set in EU legislation for construction and demolition waste and for material-specific fractions.

3.6 Product development and Ecodesign

Life cycle assessment is a useful tool also in Product development, which allows making decisions about environmental improvements and final performance.

EcoDesign directive and requirements was released in 2009, for the energy related products [53]. New Circular Action Plan [45] contains legislative initiative proposal to widen EcoDesign directive beyond energy-related products to the broadest possible range of products. Commission will consider establishing sustainability principles and other appropriate ways to regulate the following aspects, which would:

- improving product durability, reusability, upgradability and reparability, addressing the presence of hazardous chemicals in products, and increasing their energy and resource efficiency;
- **increasing recycled content in products**, while ensuring their performance and safety;
- **enabling remanufacturing and high-quality recycling**;
- reducing carbon and environmental footprints;
- restricting single-use and countering premature obsolescence;
- introducing a ban on the destruction of unsold durable goods;
- incentivising product-as-a-service or other models where producers keep the ownership of the product or the responsibility for its performance throughout its lifecycle;
- mobilising the potential of digitalisation of product information, including solutions such as digital passports, tagging and watermarks;
- rewarding products based on their different sustainability performance, including by linking high performance levels to incentives.

From construction materials, priority will be given to the intermediary products as steel, cement and chemicals but also further product groups will be identified according to their environmental impact and circularity potential.

Circularity in production processes

The Commission will enable greater circularity in industry by supporting different action. Below are actions, which related also to the BASAJAUN new innovative products:

- supporting sustainable and circular bio-based sector through the implementation of the Bio economy Action Plan,
- promoting the use of digital technologies for tracking, tracing and mapping of resources,
- promoting the uptake of green technologies through a system of solid verification by registering the EU Environmental Technology Verification scheme as an EU certification mark.

EC 'Economy Principles for building design' [54] supporting actors in the whole construction value chain by providing them principles for circular design of buildings. Principles for 'Manufacturers of construction products' related to the durability, waste reduction and management, but also for use of **harmonised materials passports and building passports**, to promote reused- and recycled materials with the same performance as natural (virgin) materials and finally avoiding using Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC), which could hamper reuse or recycling possibilities later.

4 Wooden materials

This chapter discussing about wooden material productions and their global warming potential (GWP) according to the Environmental Product Declarations. GWP indicator shows rather well production efficiency [56] and it is also one of widely used indicator showing environmental performance of building materials, -structures and buildings, moving towards low carbon construction.

Wooden materials used in building sector are sawn timber, engineered wood products and different boards. Wood materials are used in almost all building types and structures i.e., exterior- and interior walls, floors, roof constructions, load bearing structures.

4.1 By products

By-products like bark, wooden chips, sawdust, cutter shavings are generated from wood processing, where the main goal is not the production of wood by-products. Wooden by-products are not categorized as waste according to EU waste framework directive; waste defined as a substance or item, which the owner disposes of, intends to dispose of or is obligated to dispose of [2]. Utilization of woodworking industry by-products is certain. However, allocation of suitable materials to mills, processes and products is crucial for the sustainability of the forestry-wood chains. If less suitable material is allocated to a process, this will normally lead to losses in yield and value.

For example, study of Finnish sawmills shows that in certain year Finnish logs were utilized for 45% of sawn timber-, 37% of pulp-, 15% of energy- and 1% chipboard production [20]. By-product utilizations share between board and energy industries might change annually, as it depends on many factors including country specific features, trading, etc.

In environmental point of view, it is also a methodical question, how impact allocation between multi-output processes should be done (see Chapter 2.5 allocation).

4.2 Timber and structural wood

Timber

Timber is one of the main wooden building materials, which is also used for the production of engineered products. Timber production includes forest management, log transportation and timber production process. While forest management includes raising the trees, plantation, cultivation, use of fertilizers and pesticides, build up infrastructure, transportation processes, and machine maintenance, use of fuels and lubricants and finally forest certification.

Raw material of sawn timber are sawn logs, which are sorted in sawmill by the diameter, quality and length. Logs are debarked and scanned before sawing. After sawing boards are sorted by dimensions and splinting for drying. Drying is done in a kiln according wood species and dimensions. Dry timber is graded by quality. Further processing is done for dimensions and strength grading [57].

Figure 11 Process phases for sawn timber production [57]

Forest management but also sawing and drying process causing main environmental impacts and variations between sawmills. It is highly important how by-products and wastes are utilized.

Finnish and Swedish Sawn timber EPD shows the result but also impacts range between assessed sawmills, by giving impact values for the minimum and maximum cases [58], [59] (Figure 12).

For example, according to the Finnish EPD, Life cycle stage A1 for Finnish Log acquisition shows ~55% of difference between minimum and maximum GWP fossil-value and slightly less difference, ~30%, of GWP-biogenic-value. Also log transportation, life cycle stage A2, shows ~30% difference between minimum and maximum GWP fossil value [58].

Figure 12 GWP_{fossil} for Sawn timber production in Finland and Sweden (A1-3) [58], [59]

Figure 13 shows the sawn timber product stage (life cycle stage A1-3) obtained from different EPDs. All the cases represent sustainable managed forestry. Result contains data from individual sawmills but also a group of sawmills. According to the result, average GWP-value is -697 kg/m³ and difference between minimum and maximum value is about 36%.

Figure 13 GWP from the production of sawn timber (phases A1-3) [60] [61], [59], [58], [57], [62]

Structural engineered wood

Structural engineered wood products are made up of a number of layers of sawn timber (Glulam, CLT) or veneer (LVL) and layers bonded together with adhesives. The thickness of those laminates depends on the application. Common structural glulam applications are Lintels, Bearers, Roof beams, Rafters, Curves, Columns, Portal frames, Garage beams. Process flows for the Glulam production is shown in Figure 14.

Flowsheet

Figure 14 Production processes for the Glulam production (EPD from Moelven Töreboda AB) [63]

Figure 15 shows GWP result from European EPDs for glulam production and Figure 16 for LVL and CLT production (Life cycle stages A1-3). Stora Enso's CLT production data based on two Austrian factory and one Sweden factory, while LVL production based on factory in Finland.

According to the GWP, Glulam production in France and Sweden was efficient, while production was less efficient in Germany. Average GWP for assessed glulam production cases was -644 kg/m³, while best result was -660 kg/m³ and worst result -615 kg/m³ (Figure 16).

GWP for CLT production show high variation between Stora Enso's plants (in Austria and Sweden) and production in France. One possible explanation could be that Electricity production in France is based highly to the nuclear energy, which has low GWP value, but also acquisition of timber and production efficiency has a great impact to the result (Figure 17).

Figure 15 GWP for Glulam production (Life cycle stage A1-3), based on EPDs [63], [64], [65], [66]

Figure 16 LVL and CLT production (Life cycle stage A1-3), based on EPDs [67], [68], [69]

4.3 Plywood and boards

Plywood

Plywood is suitable for applications where strength, rigidity and versatility of lightweight plywood are required. Spruce building plywood is suitable for floors, walls, subfloors and roof washers.

Overlaid birch plywood (made from veneer and for example overlaid with phenol film) has a durable, wear-resistant surface, which is either smooth or has a wire mesh or embossed pattern. Smooth surface panels are used in concrete formwork, transport industry, building applications, packaging etc. Patterned surface panels are multipurpose flooring panels used in transport industry and building applications.

The plywood production consists of cutting the wood into veneer, which are then cross glued together to form boards in various thicknesses.

Manufacturing process flow diagram

Figure 17 Processes for plywood production [70]

Figure 18 GWP for Plywood life cycle stage A1-3 based on EPDs [71], [70], [72], [73], [74], [75], [76], [77]

Particle board

Particleboard is made from wood chips: from forest thinning residues, log harvesting waste, co-products of sawmilling but it could be made also from post-consumer recycled wood, pulp logs that can be engineered for specific applications.

Particleboard but also Oriented Strand board (OSB) is widely used for construction purposes. OSB is similar to particleboard as it is formed by adding adhesives and then layers of wood strands (flakes) are compressed together, but in specific orientations.

Traditionally all leftovers incurred during the board manufacture are redirected into the process or used as fuel to supply the energy needs of the manufacturing process on site. Thus, no wooden waste is generated during particleboard production process.

Particleboards and OSBs from the de-construction can be collected separately and utilised in the same purpose, in case when boards are not fully glued together. Recycling is possible when materials sorted by type, crushed and redirected to the wood materials manufacturing process.

Boards (particleboard and OSB) have a large variability of product properties and quality grades. According to the requirements, particleboards can be classified into the following use classes (EN 312):

- P1 General purpose boards for use in dry conditions,
- P2 Boards for interior fitments (including furniture) for use in dry conditions
- P3 Nonloadbearing boards for use in humid conditions
- P4 Loadbearing boards for use in dry conditions
- P5 Loadbearing boards for use in humid conditions
- P6 Heavy duty loadbearing boards for use in dry conditions
- P7 Heavy duty loadbearing boards for use in humid conditions.

And according to the OSB application requirements (EN 300), OSB classified as follows:

- OSB/1: Panels for general purposes and interior furnishings (incl. furniture) for use in dry conditions,
- OSB/2: Panels for load-bearing purposes for use in dry conditions,
- OSB/3: Panels for load-bearing purposes for use in wet conditions,
- OSB/4: High load-capacity panels for loadbearing purposes for use in wet conditions.

Particleboard and OSB EPD's representing either one board type or many types and their cover either one manufacturer, who has production units in many countries, or only one factory in one country. Figure 20 shows GWP for the particleboard- and Figure 21 for OSB production (A1-3).

Figure 19 GWP for particleboard production (Life cycle stages A1-3), based on EPDs [78], [79], [80], [81], [82]

According to the GWP, particleboard production in France was efficient, while production was less efficient in Sonae Arauco. Sonae Arauco particleboard represent their production units in Portugal, Spain and Germany (two factory) but also production in South Africa. As reported in Sonae Arauco EPD [79], particleboard consists 85% of wooden chips and 8 - 10% of glues, but 45% of GWP impacts (excluded embodied carbon) is respond from the glues.

Best GWP result, in French particleboard production, explained with the high use of recycled wood (~50%) and virgin log content is only app. 10%. In addition, also electricity consumption is beneficial in France, as electricity production has low GWP value (as based highly for nuclear energy).

Average GWP for assessed particleboard production cases was -838 kg/m^3 , while best result was -982 kg/m^3 and worst result -707 kg/m^3 .

Figure 20 GWP for OSB production (Life cycle stages A1-3) based on EPDs [83], [84], [85], [86], [87].

According to the GWP, also OSB production in France was efficient, while production was less efficient in Egger, Germany. Average GWP for assessed OSB production cases was -851 kg/m^3 , while best result was -933 kg/m^3 and worst result -753 kg/m^3 . Best result from France could explained with the electricity consumptions, which has favourable GWP value but also process efficiency.

5 Management of recovered wooden material

5.1 Quality of the recovered wood

The biggest barrier to reuse and recycling of wood waste is the high variability of the quality of recovered wood from demolition activities. Recovered wood from demolition or renovation activities can be treated with chemicals and preservatives and often contains metal fasteners such as nails, staples and screws. Moreover, the material is susceptible to degradation and the products can be damaged mechanically, by exposure to UV light or by hygro-thermal processes in the wood. Such material often does not meet the quality requirements for the new construction or wood-based product manufacturing without further processing. For these reasons, recovered wooden waste has been primarily used for energy recovery. Chipping clean wooden waste in particle boards, fibre boards or wood composites is also a good practice, but it means down-cycling.

Wood waste can be contaminated by chemicals or other materials such as plastics, metals, concrete, gypsum, and glass. Unwanted materials may be removed mechanically by manual or machine sorting. Chemical contamination, for instance paint, varnishes, coatings, preservative, glues, etc. is, however, nearly impossible to separate from the wood material [88]. The biotic or mechanical damage is often localized, and therefore the damaged parts can be easily cut and removed from the higher quality wood or repaired for instance with epoxy resin if the product shall be preserved. Important quality of the wood material is its natural colour and surface pattern that can be damaged by UV radiation or fire, but it should be noted that in some applications, photo-chemical surface modification or charring is preferred and the products may be reused.

The quality of recovered wood has different classification criteria in different countries [89], [90], [91] but at least three classes are typically recognized: untreated wood, non-hazardous treated wood and hazardous treated wood. It should be noted that the tools, equipment and material storage conditions during renovation or demolition work can significantly affect the quality of the recovered materials and products, and therefore early identification of valuable materials and components should be performed during the waste audit of the building.

5.2 Waste audit

Waste audit is assessment of construction and demolition waste streams prior to demolition or renovation of buildings and infrastructures [48]. Its purpose is to identify and quantify all possible waste streams, but it is recommended to explicitly summarize materials and products that do not become waste. Important part of the waste audit is the assessment of the quality of the materials and recommendation of the waste management (e.g. reuse, recycling, energy recovery) based on this assessment. The recommended waste management may directly affect the demolition or renovation planning, methods and equipment used, and arrangements for storage and transport. Figure 22 describes the basic steps of the waste audit. In the context of zero-waste strategy, waste audit is the most important tool for planning demolition and renovation work.

Figure 21 Elementary steps in the waste audit [48]

In order to prioritize waste hierarchy [2], waste auditor should first assume the highest level of material recovery (components) and then continue down to constituents and other materials. According to the waste audit guideline [48], the waste holder is responsible for the knowledge of the state and quality of his materials. The auditor typically provides this information, but his main responsibility is to identify recyclable and reusable materials and components (Figure 23). The contractor makes the final decision.

The manufacturers of new products from recycled materials should provide the tools for clear definition of recyclability criteria for such materials. The guidance is often developed in the industrial associations. Figure 24 illustrates this important role of the product manufacturers.

Figure 22 Responsibilities of different actors [48]

Figure 23 Link between the product manufacturer and waste auditor [48]

Examples of the possible assessment of the wood damage and suitability for reuse are provided in Table 3 and Table 4. They are based on the Australian interim industry standard [92] and Finnish research project ReUSE [93].

Table 3 Wood damage assessment according to [93]

Damage	Importance	Note
Bolt holes	mild	reduce the cross-section
Notches	severe	reduce the cross-section, cause stress concentration
Shakes (cracks from overloading) and splits	severe	require a treatment
Checks (rheological cracks)	mild	reduce the stiffness, increase the risk of biotic damage
Shape distortions	mild	difficult to fit into new structure
Biotic damage	mild to severe	usually requires a treatment

Table 4 Wood connections assessment according to [93]

Connections	Suitability for deconstruction and reuse	Note
Glued connections	not suitable	Cannot be separated without damaging the elements.
Carpentry joints	sometimes suitable	Notches can cause stress concentration if the elements are used in different configuration.
Nails, staples	sometimes suitable	Fail in bending and are therefore difficult to remove without damaging the element.
Screws	mostly suitable	The same connector is not as effective in the same hole.
Bolts, dowels	suitable	The hole and the cracks should be checked.

5.3 Wood waste prevention and reduction

According to the European waste legislation, the waste means “any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard” [2]. As long as no specific regulation exists for the certain waste type generated in a certain region, the objects or substances that are not being discarded, may keep their product status. The European Waste Framework Directive specifically distinguish between product reuse without becoming waste and product reuse as a waste recovery option called preparing for reuse. This is important for the definition of the conditions that need to be fulfilled for the wood material to keep its product status after it has been removed from the renovated or demolished building.

Figure 24 Recommended interpretation of waste and product status [source: own graphic]

The reuse process is additionally limited to the products used for the same purpose as conceived [2]. This means that many building products have to meet the requirements of the relevant harmonized technical standards in order to be reused. If the product is going to be reused for a different purpose (e.g. to comply with different standard) it may be conservatively regarded as waste (see Figure 24). The

prevention of wood waste should be always the priority for the zero-waste strategy in wood construction, but it is not the only possibility.

As illustrated in Figure 24, the waste product can be either remanufactured or recycled resulting in a new product and consequent reduction of the original amount of waste. It can be achieved by End-of-Waste process [2] or environmental permit for waste recycling. Therefore, it is recommended that the final amount of generated waste M_{out} is calculated as:

$$M_{out} = M - M_P - M_{EoW} \quad (3)$$

where M is the total mass of material removed from the building, M_P is the mass of material that retains its product status, M_{EoW} is the mass of material that ceased to be waste later on. The remaining waste accounted in M_{out} is the waste utilized in the production of new products M_R , energy production M_E and disposal M_D . For hygroscopic materials such as wood, it is recommended to use equivalent dry wood mass in the calculation. In zero-waste strategy, the ultimate goal is that M_{out} is minimized, but it is also recommended that $M_P > M_{EoW} > M_R > M_E > M_D$.

Different recycling options for wood waste will be discussed in the following sections.

Utilization of wooden by-products

The additional material streams generated as an integral part of a production process may be regarded as not being waste and called by-product if there is certain and lawful further use of them without any further processing other than normal industrial practice [2]. By-products from wood manufacturing can be for instance timber offcuts, sawdust, bark, chip or wooden dust. The advantage of such by-products is that they are not affected by the material degradation process and their origin and species is well known. Offcuts of smaller dimension can be finger-jointed into standard lengths and replace virgin timber. This may be economical especially for more exotic hardwoods [94].

Utilization of untreated solid wood

Reclaimed wood from deconstruction projects is typically the highest quality material that can be readily used in a new building. If the original certification is not available, the material may need to undergo the grading process to comply to the relevant technical standard. Material dealers may also collect scrap wood from demolition. It may be low-grade material unsuitable for structural use in large-scale projects, but as it does not require any additional processing, it may be economically competitive to virgin material for various purposes. Finally, it is always safe to shred the untreated wood waste for recycling in particleboards.

Utilization of treated or glued non-hazardous wood

Painted and glued wood (panels, veneers, chipboards, glulam, mdf-boards) have more limited use in recycling as the adhesives and paints cannot be easily removed in the shredding process. On the other hand, if carefully deconstructed, the products may be reused as such by re-planning or complete remanufacture. Over-coating of painted wood is not recommended because of possible spalling of the old underlays.

Utilization of treated hazardous wood (painted or impregnated)

When demolition produces wood material, which have been treated with hazardous substances it requires special managements and is controlled by law in many countries. The Basel Convention

Article 1, provides a list of hazardous wastes [95] by waste category. Below is a list of waste category and streams, which might be relevant for the wooden construction waste:

- Y5, Wastes from the manufacture, formulation and **use of wood preserving chemicals**;
- Y6, Wastes from the production, formulation and **use of organic solvents** should be controlled;
- Y10, Waste substances and articles **containing or contaminated** with polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and/or polychlorinated terphenyls (PCTs) and/or polybrominated biphenyls (PBBs)
- Y13, Wastes from production, formulation and **use of resins, latex, plasticizers, glues/adhesives.**

In EPD's, production of hazardous wastes should be described according to the existing applicable legislation, e.g. European Waste framework directive.

In EPDs, the declaration of material content of the product shall list as a minimum substances contained in the product that are listed in the "**Candidate List of Substances of Very High Concern for authorisation**" (SVHC), when their content exceeds the limits for registration with the European Chemicals Agency.

6 Waste wood from construction, renovation and demolition sites

6.1 Wood waste from construction sector in EU

The basic starting point, for the utilization of wooden wastes from construction sector and thus improving environmental impact from buildings, must be the information about the waste amounts and types, but also impacts from waste at different stages of the construction process. In this chapter, we are focusing only to the wood waste coming from new construction sites, renovation sites and demolition sites. Besides renovations of professional construction companies, also renovations done by households are taken account. The latter are doing decorations or improvements to their homes (minor renovations). According Eurostat [96] construction and households together are producing yearly 10-14 Mt wood waste. Of it 98% is non-hazardous and 2% hazardous (Figure 26). Germany, France, Netherlands, UK, Italy and Sweden are producing 85% of wood waste (Figure 27). Many countries do not report any wood waste. The amount indicated by the statistics is probably underestimation.

Figure 25 Wood waste from construction sector and minor renovation of households [96]

Figure 26 Wood waste from construction sector and minor renovation of households by member states [96]

The wood waste has been seen as a fuel for energy production. In that context, it is classified on the basis of treatment [89]. The two best fuels are untreated waste wood (class A) or treated wood as well as wood products (B) without harmful surface treatment (like organic halogens or heavy metals). They are also those, what can be recycled to new construction products (Figure 28).

Figure 27 Classification of waste wood coming from construction, renovation and demolition sites

In this chapter, the same classification is used. The amount of waste wood is adopted from Eurostat (Figure 27). BASAJAUN partners from Germany, Finland and Spain have estimated the distribution to the classes:

Class A in this context: only mechanically treated wood.

- surplus timber from construction sites
- wooden frame structures and roof chairs from renovation and demolition sites.

Class B in this context: treated wood and processed, treated wood (like chipboards) are separated from each other.

- treated wooden facades and wooden interior surfaces from renovation and demolition sites
- wooden building boards from all construction sites.

This assessment has been made because quality determines where wood waste can be used, either as a material or as a raw material (Figure 29).

Figure 28 Flow chart how to determinate different waste wood categories

6.2 Country case studies

Case of Finland

This study is focused on Finland and even so that the method itself is quite general in scope, the result depends on specific local circumstances or parameters (like traditionally used building materials, renovation culture, age and size of the building stock, building regulations and their evolution etc.).

The wood waste coming from new construction sites, renovation sites and demolition sites have been studied in collaboration with construction companies and waste management sector. Besides construction companies, also households produce wood waste when they are when they renovating the interior of their homes [97], [98], [99]. Altogether, these activities produce 293 000 t non-hazardous wood waste and less than one-ton hazardous waste (Table 5). Of it 15% comes from new construction sites (Life cycle phase A4-5), 20% from renovation sites and 10% from dismantling the interior within home improvement projects (Life cycle phase B) and 55% from building demolitions (Life cycle phase C1-4).

VTT sorted the construction wood waste to types by using use market studies. The most important of them is Finnish building stock as carbon sink [29]. The most of non-hazardous wood waste measured

in tonnes is clean lumber (125 200 tonnes) and is coming from new construction sites as well as from building demolition sites. Various ways treated and processed wood waste (167 750 tonnes) is coming from renovation sites, demolition sites and home improvement projects (Table 6).

Table 5 Wood waste from construction sector and households in Finland [96]

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (CDW) and from households (decoration -type renovations) [in tonnes]				Hazardous wood waste (from CDW) Total
Year	from CDW	from Households	Total	
2012	237 000	30 000	267 000	1 000
2014	379 000	28 000	407 000	1 065
2016	264 000	29 000	293 000	nn

Table 6 Wood waste types by building life cycle phases in Finland [96][127]

Types of wood waste		A-C total	A4-5	B	C1-4
Clean lumber (frame materials, other clean)	45 %	125 250	30 800	5 900	88 550
Painted or ceased lumber (facade or indoor panels; window frames)	35 %	102 050	4 400	41 300	56 350
Processed wood (chipboards, fibreboards, laminates)	20 %	65 700	8 800	40 800	16 100
Total	100 %	293 000	44 000	88 000	161 000

In terms of environmental impact, the processing of raw wood into construction products causes emissions that warm the climate. On the other hand, wood products are useful carbon storages. The amount of wood waste is transformed to the global warming potential (GWP) and lost carbon storage by coefficients (Table 7).

The GWP is defined as the ratio of the time-integrated radiative forcing from the instantaneous release of 1 kg of a trace substance relative to that of 1 kg of a reference gas. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) provides the generally accepted values for GWP.

Table 7 Global warming potential and lost carbon storage by building life cycle phases in Finland [128]

Parameter	Clean lumber	Painted or ceased lumber	Processed wood	Total
Construction and demolition wood waste [tonnes]				
A5-C1 total	125 250	102 050	65 700	293 000
A5	30 800	4 400	8 800	44 000
B3-5	5 900	41 300	40 800	88 000
C1	88 550	56 350	16 100	161 000
Global warming potential				
Material density, kg/m ³	460	460	580	
Unit GWP, kg/kg	0.06	0.06	0.63	
A5-C1 total	7 890	6 430	41 690	56 010
A5	1 940	280	5 580	7 800
B3-5	370	2 600	25 890	28 860
C1	5 580	3 550	10 220	19 350
Lost carbon storage [CO₂]				
Stored carbon, kg CO ₂ /kg	1.58	1.56	0.72	
A5-C1 total	197 950	159 670	47 090	404 710
A5	48 680	6 880	6 310	61 870
B3-5	9 320	64 620	29 240	103 180
C1	139 950	88 170	11 540	239 660

Case of Germany

The wood waste coming from new construction sites, renovation sites (incl. renovations of households) and demolition sites consists 30% of all wood waste in Germany [96]. Altogether these activities produce around 3 873 000 t tons of waste wood (Table 8).

Table 8 Wood waste from construction sector and households in Germany [96]

year	Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW) and from households (decoration -type renovations) [in tonnes]			Hazardous wood waste (from CDW) Total
	from CDW	from Households	Total	
2012	2 916 000	625 000	3 541 000	13 000
2014	3 043 000	735 000	3 778 000	13 000
2016	3 207 000	666 000	3 873 000	10 000

The German waste wood act classifies [100] waste wood into four categories AI, AII, AIII, AIV and additionally considers waste wood containing PCB. The following Table 9 shows a more detailed explanation of the categories and gives examples for the classification of wooden materials and products from the construction sector.

Table 9 Waste wood categories in the German waste wood act [100]

Category	Description
A I	Untreated or only mechanically processed waste wood that has been contaminated with substances foreign to wood to a not inconsiderable extent during its use E.g.: Building site assortments e.g.: natural solid wood
A II	Glued, painted, coated, varnished or otherwise treated waste wood without halogen-organic compounds in the coating and without wood preservatives Building site assortments e.g.: Wood-based materials, shuttering wood, treated solid wood (without harmful contamination); chipboards Waste wood from deconstruction and demolition e.g.: Floorboards, dead floors, board formwork from the interior finishing (without harmful contamination) door leaves and frames (without harmful contamination) Profile sheets for the interior design, ceiling panels, decorative beams etc.(without harmful contamination)
A III	Waste wood with organo-halogen compounds in the coating without wood preservatives E.g.: furniture, with organo-halogen compounds in the coating
A IV	Waste wood treated with wood preservatives, such as railway sleepers, poles, hop poles, vine stakes, as well as other waste wood that cannot be assigned to categories A I, A II or A III due to its pollutant load, with the exception of waste PCB waste wood E.g.: Construction wood for load-bearing parts; wooden truss and rafter; Windows, windowsills, exterior doors; Impregnated construction wood from outdoors; Construction and demolition wood with hazardous contamination
Waste wood containing PCB	E.g.: Insulation and noise protection panels treated with substances including polychlorinated biphenyls

As the Table 10 below shows, 17% of the wood waste is categorized in class AI, 34.7% in AII. 31.4% of the German wood waste is considered to class AIII and wood waste of class AIV shows a share of 16.70%. The environmental impacts are estimated to each category (Table 11).

Table 10 Share of waste wood [% of tonnes] per waste wood categories in Germany (expert estimation)

Waste wood class	Total
AI (e.g. natural solid wood)	17.0%
AII (e.g. door leaves and frames (without harmful contamination, chipboards)	34.7%
AIII (e.g. furniture, with organo-halogen compounds in the coating)	31.4%
AIV (e.g. construction wood for load-bearing part	16.7%
Waste wood containing PCB	0.1%
Total	100%

Table 11 Global warming potential and lost carbon storage per wood waste types in Germany (building life cycle phases together) [128]

Parameter	A I	A II	A III	A IV	Total
Share of total	17 %	35 %	31 %	17 %	100 %
Construction and demolition wood waste [tonnes]					
A5-C1 total	658 000	1 344 000	1 216 000	647 000	3 865 000
Global warming potential					
Material density, kg/m ³	460	460	580	460	
Unit GWP, kg/kg	0.06	0.06	0.63	0.06	
A5-C1 total	41 500	852 700	771 500	40 800	1 706 500
Lost carbon storage [CO ₂]					
Stored carbon, kg CO ₂ /kg	1.58	1.56	0.72		
A5-C1 total	1 039 900	963 300	871 500	1 012 300	3 887 000

Case of Spain

The total amount of construction wood waste in Spain is 237 000 t (Table 12). Amount of wood waste by building life cycle phase (Table 13). Detailed description of wood waste quality is following:

- New construction sites: estimated 3%. Type of products and applications: pallets, frameworks and wood foundations, wooden made building structures (glued parts, modular parts combined with concrete and so on).
- Renovation sites (material wastage): estimated 12%. Type of products and applications: Light building structures (partition elements), carpentry products, doors and other wooden products. Over the last years, in residential buildings wooden formworks are being retired because of the action of xilofagus.
- Demolition of buildings: estimated 45%. Type of products and applications: structure in general. The majority of wooden products placed in building are more than 60 years old.
- Renovation of homes: estimated 40%.

Table 12 Wood waste from construction sector and households in Spain [96]

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW) and from households (decoration -type renovations) [tonnes]				Hazardous wood waste (from CDW) Total
year	from CDW	from Households	Total	
2012	106 000	131 000	237 000	1 000
2014	59 000	89 000	148 000	nn
2016	142 000	95 000	237 000	nn

Table 13 Wood waste by building life cycle phases in Spain (expert estimation)

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (CDW) and home renovations		
New construction sites (A4-5)	3 %	7 100
Renovation sites (B)	12 %	28 300
Demolition of buildings (C1-4)	45 %	106 200
Decoration of homes (B)	40 %	95 000
Total	100 %	237 000

Detailed description of wood waste quality is following (Table 13):

- Clean lumber (frame materials, other clean): estimated 5%. Type of products and applications: minority of wooden products placed in the building are not treated. Normally, they have their own treatments (coatings, preservatives, flame retardants) to meet requirements and extend their life performance.
- Painted or ceased lumber (facade or indoor panels): estimated 70%. Type of products and applications: preservatives (xilofagus protection), paints, flame retardants, façades for outdoor performance and humidity protective treatments
- Processed wood (chipboards, fibreboards, laminates): estimated 25%. Type of products and applications: the amount is increasing every year; big product waste is normally found; wood boards, furniture, secondary doors, MDF and other wood waste. Doors from carpentry, window frames and partitions also are some examples of products here.

Table 14 Global warming potential and lost carbon storage by wood waste types in Spain (building life cycle phases together) [128]

Parameter	Clean lumber	Painted or ceased lumber	Processed wood	Total
Shares	5 %	20 %	75 %	100 %
Construction and demolition wood waste [tonnes]				
A5-C1 total	12 000	47 000	178 000	237 000
Global warming potential				
Material density, kg/m ³	460	460	580	
Unit GWP, kg/kg	0.06	0.06	0.63	
A5-C1 total	800	3 000	112 900	116 700
Lost carbon storage [CO ₂]				
Stored carbon, kg CO ₂ /kg	1.58	1.56	0.72	
A5-C1 total	19 000	73 500	127 600	220 100

Case of Poland

The wood waste coming from new construction sites, renovation sites and demolition sites. Altogether, these activities produce 71 000 t non-hazardous in Poland (Table 15). Of it 10% comes from new

construction sites (Life cycle phase A4-5), 25% from renovation sites (Life cycle phase B) and 65% from building demolitions (Life cycle phase C1-4).

The most of non-hazardous wood waste measured in tonnes is treated lumber (39 000 tonnes) and is coming from building demolition sites (Table 16). Also amount of processed wood waste (21 000 tonnes) is larger than clean lumber (4000 tonnes). The environmental impacts are estimated to each category (Table 17).

Table 15 Wood waste from construction sector in Poland [96]

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW) and from households (decoration -type renovations) [tonnes]				Hazardous wood waste (from CDW) Total
year	from CDW	from Households	Total	
2012	28 000	nn	28 000	nn
2014	43 000	nn	43 000	nn
2016	71 000	nn	71 000	nn

Table 16 Wood waste by building life cycle phases in Poland (expert estimation)

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW)		
New construction sites (A4-5)	10 %	7 000
Renovation sites (B)	25 %	18 000
Demolition of buildings (C1-4)	65 %	46 000
Total	100 %	71 000

Table 17 Global warming potential and lost carbon storage by wood waste types in Poland (building life cycle phases together) [128]

Parameter	Clean lumber	Painted or ceased lumber	Processed wood	Other	Total
Share of total	5 %	55 %	30 %	10 %	100 %
Construction and demolition wood waste [tonnes]					
A5-C1 total	4 000	39 000	21 000	7 000	71 000
Global warming potential					
Material density, kg/m ³	460	460	580	580	
Unit GWP, kg/kg	0.06	0.06	0.63	0.63	
A5-C1 total	300	2 500	13 300	4 400	20 500
Lost carbon storage [CO₂]					
Stored carbon, kg CO ₂ /kg	1.58	1.56	0.72	0.72	
A5-C1 total	6 300	61 000	15 100	5 000	87 400

Case of France

The building sector is an important source of waste. In total, new construction sites, renovation sites and demolition sites generate 2 572 000 t non-hazardous wood waste in France (Table 18).

- From construction sites, there are mainly wood waste from packaging, residues of construction elements (timber frame, roofing, sheeting, and flooring) and elements of support (concrete forming, temporary walk floors). The wood wastes from construction sites are potentially less contaminated compared to demolition wastes.
- From demolition sites, there are end of life products (carpentry, joinery, floors ...).
- In renovation projects, waste wood is partly demolition waste and partly construction waste. This is the reason, why French demolition wood waste is not exactly distributed to building life cycle phases (Table 19).

Table 18 Wood waste from construction sector and households in France [96]

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW) and from households (decoration -type renovations) [tonnes]				Hazardous wood waste (from CDW) Total
year	from CDW	from Households	Total	
2012	1 782 000	840 000	2 622 000	64 000
2014	1 615 000	917 000	2 532 000	nn
2016	1 592 000	980 000	2 572 000	nn

Table 19 Wood waste by building life cycle phases in France [102]

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW) and home renovations		
New construction and renovation sites (A4-5; B)	9 %	239 000
Demolition of buildings and tearing structures in renovation sites (C1-4; B)	53 %	1 353 000
Decoration of homes (B)	38 %	980 000
Total	100 %	2 572 000

Case of Sweden

The wood waste coming from new construction sites, renovation sites and demolition sites. Altogether, these activities produce 851 000 t non-hazardous wood waste in Sweden (Table 20).

Table 20 Wood waste from construction sector and households in Sweden [96]

Wood waste from construction and demolition sites (C&DW) and from households (decoration -type renovations) [tonnes]				Hazardous wood waste (from CDW) Total
year	from CDW	from Households	Total	
2012	300 000	nn	300 000	87 000
2014	200 000	412 000	612 000	92 000
2016	430 000	421 000	851 000	45 000

6.3 EU level benefits and future

Europe consumed total 43 Mt sawn wood and same the amount, 43 Mt wood-based panels in 2016 [103]. According Eurostat [90] the amount of available wood waste was 2016 about 14 Mt (9 Mt from construction sector and 4 Mt from dwelling renovations of households). Compared to the total consumption of sawn wood and wood-based panels, annually available wood waste represents a significant material resource. In terms of environmental impact, wood products are useful carbon storages. By reusing and recycling wood waste, we can save at EU level 9.0 Mt carbon storage and reduce the global warming potential (GWP) by 3.8 Mt.

For decades at European level, as well as global level, the social megatrend has been urbanization. In building construction, this means more apartment buildings than single-family homes. Concrete, steel or aluminium have taken market share from wood frames, gypsum from wood-based panels. In addition, complex sandwich structures and other functional laminates have been introduced to market. When we compound social changes and the generic material development, we may assume that the amount of wood waste will not increase in coming years. The present green building wave [33] with the appreciation of wood will produce more wood waste from construction sector only after decades but will increase opportunities to utilize wood waste already now.

7 BASAJAUN wooden products

This chapter discussing about BASAJAUN products (Foam formed insulation, Foam formed wood-plastic composite, Thermoplastic composite, Structural Insulation Panel), which are based on wooden materials, either from virgin origin or from the wooden waste streams (process wastes, construction and demolition wastes). Approximate and theoretical GWP assessment is made for foam formed insulation and SIP panel. Other assessments based on literature. In time being BASAJAUN product development work was ongoing and thus the results presented here are not final.

Typically wood based products utilizing their by-product energy contents inside the process for heat production and timber drying. Thus, reducing the need for purchased energy gives to the product some benefits compared to those using fossil based energy. According to the product performances, those new BASAJAUN products will possibly substitute traditionally used materials. The key question is does new products obtain lower impacts (GWP) than traditionally used products.

$$GWP_{\text{BASAJAUN}} \leq GWP_{\text{traditional}}$$

Full Life cycle assessment for BASAJAUN products will be presented in BASAJAUN deliverable D2.4.

7.1 Foam formed insulations (Soprema)

Foam forming technology is used for manufacturing novel wood based highly porous material, which can be used as thermal insulation material at least in ceilings and walls. The thermal conductivity (lambda value) of insulation panel is more or less comparable to commercial mineral wool materials (glass and stone wool). The best measured lambda value for foam formed insulation material at the moment is 0.034 W/(mK), which is about 15 % lower (better) than best values for commercially available wood-based insulation materials. Commercial glass- and stone wool, expanded polystyrene and wood based thermal insulation materials can be substituted by this novel material. The main benefits of this new material compared to existing commercial thermal insulation materials are:

- Sustainable, recyclable and health solution compared to mineral wools (high embodied energy amount, problems with end use, sensitizer emissions);
- Approximately 15 % better insulation properties compared to wood-based insulation materials produced by water-based process (high density);
- Sustainable and recyclable compared to wood-based insulation materials produced by dry process (include 10-30 % synthetic fibres);
- Sustainable compared to expanded polystyrene (oil-based material).

In principle foam formed thermal insulation panel is recyclable and recycled wood can be utilized as a raw material in the production of new insulation panels. These both features will reduce carbon dioxide emissions and the amount of waste.

GWP assessment

GWP was calculated for the foam formed insulation material for the case of virgin sawdust and recycled wood. Variations in the transportation distance, between the material producer and insulation manufacturing, but also variations between different electricity production methods is also assessed.

The calculations were made according to the EN 15804+A2 [19] standard, using SULCA assessment tool [104] and stored carbon, according to EN 16485:2014 [25]. Also the calculations were made only for the production part, i.e. cradle to gate.

The materials data was gathered from Ecoinvent v. 3.5 and product contain following materials:

- 90% of sawdust or wooden construction waste,
- 8 % fire retardant, Boric acid, anhydrous powder, at plant (RER)
- 2% of Sodium sulphate production from natural resources.

Raw material Transportation

The distances used for the transportation of saw dust were 100km, 300km, 500km and 1000km and it was calculated with a 25t semi-trailer, EURO class VI. The trailer was calculated to be 50% filled when transporting the sawdust and the return was calculated to be empty for 30% of the distance. The transportation of sodium sulphate was expected to be 500km, with a 25t semi-trailer, EURO class VI. The trailer was calculated to be 80% filled and the return was calculated to be empty for 30% of the distance. Boric acid was calculated to be produced in Turkey and transported first 2400km with a 25t semi trailer, EURO class VI, 900km with a tanker and 300km with a 25t semi-trailer, EURO class VI. Loading was estimated to be full (100%) and the return to be empty 30% of the distance for all transports with boric acid.

Manufacturing

a)

b)

Figure 29 Manufacturing process phases for a) saw dust and b) construction wooden waste-based insulation.

Energy use

It is considered that manufacturing of product consumes electricity and natural gas as follows

- Sawdust based manufacturing: electricity 2.25 kWh/kg and natural gas 4.4 kWh/kg
- Construction wooden waste-based manufacturing: electricity 2.27 kWh/kg and natural gas 4.4 kWh/kg

Electricity is consumed in crushing, refining and product manufacturing phases. Natural gas is used in drying phase, which is one phase belongs to product manufacturing. Finnish average electricity has been calculated by VTT and according to it (year 2018), GWP emission of electricity is 115 g / kWh. For

other countries, it was assumed that electricity generation would generate 200 g / kWh, 300 g / kWh and 500 g / kWh GWP emissions.

Results

GWP assessment results for the foam formed insulation production (life cycle stages A1-3) are given in Figures 31 and 32.

Figure 30 GWP impact of transportation distances for the insulation production from virgin and recycled wooden source (Life cycle stages A1-3).

Figure 31 GWP impact of energy production method for the insulation production from virgin and recycled wooden source (life cycle stages A1-3)

Results show that optimal material utilization may depend on local and/or country specific issues - such as for example, electricity production method and transportation distances in material sourcing.

Transportation distance from 100 km to 1000 km raises GWP value 4% and 6%, correspondingly for the insulations produced from the virgin sawdust and from the wood waste. Electricity production method raises GWP impacts much more and impact was almost 40% higher for the case when electricity production method was unfavourable (500 g CO₂e/kWh than only 115 g CO₂e/kWh) and for both wood fibre source.

All cases show that insulation from waste wood has lower GWP than insulation from virgin sources.

7.2 Foam formed wood-plastic composites (Elastopoli)

Elastopoli is using the foamed wet web forming process to create material and products for building applications. In the extrusion process, the main products are extruded profiles that can be used as building profiles such as window panels, structural elements or facades. Also, in combination with the foamed panel that VTT is producing these two developments can be combined into a SIP panel. These products will be replacing conventional structural elements and panels made from wood or foamed thermoset plastics in the market. For the extruded products, a non-halogen-based fire retardant will be introduced and applied to the end products according to the territorial building codes.

Another application of the process is the sheet form composites that can flexibly incorporate many fibre materials (Lyocell, Bic-PET, viscose, recycled fibres etc.) mixed in the foaming process. The main application for this is replacing the laminates on interior products like cabinet doors. The sheet can be applied on the surfaces by using the hot-pressing process and both surface properties and visuals can be altered by using different materials in the foamed forming process.

First tests have been conducted at Fraunhofer with positive results.

Figure 32 First hot pressing trials of the sheet composite on plywood [WKL]

The reduction in global warming potential (GWP) concerning Elastopoli's process and products, it is used to make is dependent on three factors:

- the Wet Web Forming process,
- the materials used in the process,
- products and their processing.

Production process

The Wet Web Forming process Elastopoli has patented is utilizing the foaming process in BASAJAUN project. The main factors reducing GWP are as follows:

- The process can utilize never dried cellulose directly from the pulping process which means that the pulp does not have to be dried before the process as opposed to many composite technologies that utilize dried cellulose in bales.
- The raw material (cellulose) is used on site, which cuts down the logistics needs. The raw material is pumped directly from the pulping process to composite process via dedicated pipeline.
- Pulp mills create surplus electrical carbon neutral or negative energy and heat (steam) that can be used in the composite process.
- Typically, cellulose fibres are sourced locally, 200 km radius of the plant saving on logistic costs.
- Cellulose fibres are renewable and sourced from sustainably managed forests.
- The process can flexibly utilize other side streams and waste materials ranging from straw-based cellulose to wood powder of plywood dust/grind, textile waste, waste from building materials and combinations thereof. This has been tested by Elastopoli previously together with Finnish furniture company ISKU in collaboration with Fortum recycled Circo plastics.

Figure 33 ISKU student chair manufactured with cellulose reinforcement (red), plywood waste (light brown) and textile waste (dark brown)

Materials and GWP

In the BASAJAUN project, Elastopoli has worked with post-consumer waste, Circo recycled plastics. GWP impact of recycled plastics is about 50% less of the corresponding virgin plastics and fossil source depletion is only 6-7% of the corresponding virgin plastics [105].

Figure 34 GWP for virgin and recycling plastics [105]

Figure 35 Fossil fuel depletion for virgin and recycled plastics [105]

When recycled plastics are combined with cellulose/wood-based side stream materials, the final materials are fully recyclable for primary uses. This means that for example cellulose reinforced recycled PP based composite can be recycled 6-7 times without losing of its mechanical properties. This reduces the need for virgin materials in the production cycle thus reducing the carbon footprint of the products.

Foam formed wood-plastic composites is not fully developed in time being but according to the literature results, recycling plastic cases show less GWP than those from virgin sources.

7.3 Thermoplastic composites (WKI)

Overview

As part of the BASAJAUN project, Fraunhofer WKI developing a composite product based on poplar and pine plywood provided by Spanish company GARNICA. At present, plywood is covered with high pressure laminate (HPL) or other phenolic types of paper. For some applications, this product may be over-engineered and too expensive. Hence, it was decided as part of the BASAJAUN project, to develop plywood coated with a top sheet layer composed of bio composite material. The main focus is to develop a fire-retarded product which may reach classification B-s2, d0 according to the single-burning item test (SBI) based on EN 13823 [106]. In addition to a high level of fire-retardancy, other properties are sought, e.g., good adhesion to the substrate, high scratch resistance, low water uptake and swelling and high durability. The first step is to achieve good bonding of the bio composite sheets on the plywood core. Several trials have been performed using a hot-press at Fraunhofer WKI. The sheets are produced either by pressing granulate directly on top of plywood, or by pressing or gluing the finished sheets onto plywood.

In general, bio-composites consist of a thermoplastic matrix and a wood filler or reinforcement. The matrix can be of bio-based origin as in the case of polylactic acid, for example, or of recycled origin. Recyclates of thermoplastic materials such as high- and low-density polyethylene (HDPE, LDPE) and polypropylene (PP) exist in large quantities today, however, depending on the quality (post processing vs. post-consumer), differences pertaining to the quality exist. In addition, often recycle mixtures are available due to technical (level of sorting) and economic issues.

Approach in BASAJAUN Project

Fraunhofer WKI is currently evaluating different types of biopolymers as well as fossil-based plastics in combination with wood particles, fire-retardants and additives. In principle, wood residues from milling operations (e.g., plywood and LVL production) could be used instead of virgin wood particles, which would be beneficial in terms of an LCA for the final product. However, considering that the virgin wood particles stem from sawmill operations and are therefore side products or residues themselves, the carbon dioxide savings potential may already be considered high to start with.

The main challenge in using wood residues from milling operations is that the material is not homogeneous, i.e., the wood particles are contaminated with different types of thermoset adhesives, fire-retardants and other additives. Before such milling residues can be used, they need to be sorted and classified.

The developed product (plywood with top layer) has the potential to be recycled since the wood core and the top sheet can be ground, heated, plasticized and re-shaped again. However, prior to this, the top layer would probably need to be separated from the core to ensure consistent quality of the new mixtures. In theory, the complete product (core and top layer) can be ground and re-used if the material composition is known. This is an advantage compared to HPL-covered products, which are thermoset, so the products after use are more difficult to recycle.

Recycling of WPC/bio composites, life-cycle assessment (LCA)

In general, recycling of WPC is well possible due to the thermoplastic polymer matrix. Regarding processing, internal and end-of-life recycling need to be distinguished. Internal recycling refers to re-

use of materials during the production whereas end-of-life recycling addresses the re-use of materials and products after their service life. Many WPC producers are performing internal recycling because of the achievable level of material performance and cost savings. A lot of publications deal with internal recycling of WPC (for example, Augier et al. 2007 [107], Bourmaud and Baley 2007 [108] and 2009 [109], Englund and Villechevrolle 2011 [110], Beg and Pickering 2008 a [111] and 2008b [112]). Most of these publications have shown that after re-extrusion, the mechanical properties of the composites are improved and water uptake is reduced, due to improved dispersion of wood particles in the matrix, increased thermal exposure of the wood particles (reduction in hydrophilicity) and cross-linking. Only after a number of reprocessing cycles, mechanical properties are affected which is mostly due to thermal and mechanical degradation of the polymer matrix.

End-of-life recycling of WPC is not yet solved probably because the amounts of recycled materials available at present are considered too small for recycling companies and because of efforts required to collect and separate WPC based on different matrices. Most manufacturers recommend that small quantities of WPC are disposed of via the household waste system, and that larger quantities are disposed of either as recyclable waste wood material or as heat source ("energy recycling"). A specific waste legislation for WPC does not exist at present, at least not in Germany.

Regarding life-cycle assessment (LCA) of WPC, limited information is available at present. Xu et al. (2008) [113] based their study on wood fibre-reinforced PP preforms produced by compression moulding. They introduced a term called „material service density“, which is defined as the volume of material satisfying a specific strength requirement. When material service density was used as basis, the composite demonstrated superior environmental friendliness compared to pure PP.

Bolin and Smith (2011) [114] compared alkaline copper quaternary (ACQ)-treated lumber used for decking with WPC decking. They determined that under the assumptions of their LCA, the use of ACQ-treated lumber for decking offers lower fossil fuel use and environmental impacts than WPC.

Mahalle et al. (2014) [115] addressed wood fibre-reinforced PLA and PLA/thermoplastic starch (TPS) biocomposites, including a comparison to neat PP. PLA was found to cause more environmental burden than TPS. Environmental performance of the biocomposite can be improved by substituting locally available TPS for PLA. The composite can outperform neat PP in all impact categories except eutrophication effects.

7.4 Structural Insulation Panel (Garnica)

Garnica produces plywood, Garnica Brick and Garnica Ultralight product for light board. Applications that can be made with plywood are furniture, coatings, formwork, packaging and applications applicable to Structural Insulation Panels (SIP) are use as brick and structural panel.

Garnica manufactures plywood from poplar and pine and to a much lesser eucalyptus. Garnica also consumes temperate and tropical species veneer. The consumption of temperate species (mostly eucalyptus, maple and birch) has increased in the past years whereas the trend has been the opposite for tropical veneers (okume, ilomba and fromager).

Garnica has a full control over the supply chain for poplar as it purchases standing timber. For pine and eucalyptus Garnica relies on suppliers. For poplar plantations the wood that is larger than 20 cm

in diameter at the smaller end is sent to the plywood or veneer factory. Logs between 14 and 20 diameters are sold to sawmills. Smaller logs and branches are sold to chipboard or mdf manufacturers or chipped on site. These chips are either consumed by other panel manufacturers or sold as biomass. By-products from the mill are either sold or burnt in the boilers of the factory to produce the thermal energy required for the presses and in particular the driers which are the largest consumers of energy in the factories.

Other raw materials include glues and its multiple components, varnish, packaging materials, etc.

In a nutshell: 100% of the wood material is either used in the production process or sold as a by-product to other wood products or biomass clients.

Waste from production

Apart from the waste generated during the forest management, during the process of creating the plywood, surpluses are generated from the cut sheets, sanding dust, rejected material that enters the same dynamics of the forest waste, re-using it as biomass in the factories themselves or as raw material for particle board and the like.

Assembly processes of product if under your control

Garnica manufactures GBrick structural panels from the plywood and core boards of XPS. Waste from assembly Remains of material resulting from cutting the SIP panels, being a set of plywood and XPS.

GWP assessment for SIP

The GWP assessment compares a SIP panel with four different thermal insulation options: foam formed insulation from virgin sawdust, foam formed insulation from wooden waste, XPS and mineral wool insulation. The thermal **transmittance** of the SIP panel complied with Finnish requirements and thus the U-value was 0.16 W/mK. The SIP panel consisted of plywood (18 mm) on both sides and an insulating layer (200 mm), in the case of mineral wool insulation and wood-based insulation (sawdust and wood waste) an additional wood structure (2 x 50x125mm k600mm) was used. The assessment assumes a lambda value for all types of insulation of 0.035 W/mK.

The assessment was made for the case where the raw materials are delivered to the SIP plant at a distance of 100 km, additionally 30% of the empty load from return is also distributed (allocated) to SIP.

Figure 36 GWP for SIP panel production phase (Life cycle stages A1-3)

The result shows that a SIP panel with a recycled insulation source has the same GWP as a Virgin wood source. The estimate is based on the assumption that the collection distance for wood waste is the same as for sawdust, but it can be much longer when the source of waste wood is construction and demolition waste. A SIP panel with BASAJAUN insulation (both options) results in a slightly higher GWP result than SIP with mineral wool, but their stored carbon (calculated as GWP biogenic) is much higher than traditional SIP with XPS or mineral wool.

8 Obstacles and opportunities for reuse and recycling

Barriers and drivers were also analysed broader in BASAJAUN work package 1, task 1.3 entitled as 'Guidelines to foster building with wood' [33]. In the work, opportunities and barriers to the increase in the use of wood in construction were analysed in four aspects, i.e. technical, societal, economic, and political. The report is based on results from two questionnaires, directed to wood construction producers and end-users, and complemented with a desk research.

In this section barriers and drivers are discussed for each lifecycle phase mainly from a technical and legislative point of view. This sector focussed on recycling in new products and reuse as product, based on information published in recent literature.

Key message

- Currently the biggest barriers are economic, due to a lack of demand for recovered waste and poor quality due to impurities and the risk for contaminants.
- Actions for improving quality include requirement for selective demolition and tracing of materials in the value chain, also a need for a quality assurance concept
- Policy measures may have a strong influence on market conditions, for example, through taxes on virgin materials.
- Other policy measures are the encouragement of green public procurement, taxes for landfilling, end-of-waste criteria and extended product responsibility (EPR), which has been introduced for many product areas

In future, actions related to material efficiency in all phases of the lifecycle need to be looked over.

Current status: Reuse and recycling of wooden materials from constructions

1. To a minor extent, timber structures (e.g. beams) and interiors (doors, windows) are reused today. Outcomes of project DemoWood indicate that the reuse rate of recovered wood is up to 38% in some countries [116] According to the Dephi survey conducted in Finland in ReUSE project [93], the likely reuse rate in Finland in 2050 will be 10-15% of concrete, 15-20% of steel and 10-20% of wood structural elements [117].

2. Some wooden building components (e.g. doors), structural timber (e.g. beams), wooden floors, façade cladding and panelling (e.g. barn wood) can be reused as such or repurposed. Rough treatment and mixing with the other materials reduces the value of recovered timber. Example of wooden products that have a reuse potential:

- Wooden beams. These can also be remanufactured to woods planks.
- Barnwood (planks from old wooden barns).
- Wooden floors

- Scaffolding wood
- Wooden doors and windows

3. Wooden materials can be recycled in particleboards, but currently not extensively recycled due to abundance of virgin material, transport costs, quality issues (paint, nails). Research is going on to develop new products (e.g., panels, wood-plastic composites) by using fibres from wood CDW and there are already products on the market. However, the recyclability of these products needs also to be assessed, especially if the wood fibres are mixed with other materials.

Examples of barriers and drivers identified at different lifecycle stages are collated in Table 21 based on information presented in literature (Wahlström et al 2020) [118], (Wahlström et al 2019) [119], (Deloitte) [93] and previous EU projects (EU HISER; EU IRCOW).

Table 21 Drivers and barriers for wooden products reuse and wooden material recycling

Feature	Drivers/benefits	Barriers/challenges
Legislation, standards	Design/manufacturing/construction phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - national policies (e.g. in Finland) support use of wooden materials in constructions (e.g. schools). Also, circular economy actions in national strategies promotes uptake of recovered materials/products in all phases - material specific recycling targets under assessment (Waste Framework Directive) - Green public procurement 	Design/manufacturing/construction phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of standards for supporting reuse, scope of standards not including reusable materials, unsuitable methods - lack of information on fulfilling indoor quality requirement in case of use in application were exposure to indoor possible - lack of traceability systems for reusable products, recyclability waste
	End-of-life phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - waste auditing recommended in many member states for resource mapping supporting selective demolition for recovery of pure material fractions - landfill bans for biodegradable waste - Reduced value added tax (VAT) rate for some recycled products (Belgium) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE-marking difficult due to lacking knowledge of previous production conditions (factory product control) - waste status of reusable products, recyclable waste End-of-life phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presence of toxic substances limiting reuse/recycling
Market/economy	Design/manufacturing/construction phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in some countries under discussion: Nordic Swan, EU Eco Label to promote reuse and recycling - wooden products preferable in some constructions as “environmentally friendly” (e.g. schools in Finland) - new jobs 	Design/manufacturing/construction phase: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - costs for virgin contra recyclable materials due to transport and processing (in some countries abundance of wooden materials makes virgin materials preferable) - guaranteed supply of products/materials
	End-of-life phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - new jobs in material upgrading/processing 	End-of-life phase <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - see above - wooden waste used as fuels

Feature	Drivers/benefits	Barriers/challenges
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in some cases, reuse is cheaper than demolition
Quality	<p>All phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traceability systems available in some countries (e.g. Tracimat in Belgium to also cover beams) 	<p>All phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of documented information available regarding the origins of waste and also data on the composition of historical construction products. - Variable quality of feedstock, risk of contamination and material degradation (e.g. mould)
Technical	<p>Design/manufacturing/construction phase</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BIM will support reuse/recycling in future <p>End-of-life phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New technologies developed (several R&D project ongoing, e.g. BASAJAUN, HISER; ICEBERG; . - BIM under development to cover recycling aspects. 	<p>All phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - demonstration cases lacking - down-cycling in recycling (no information on recyclability loops)
Awareness, knowledge	<p>All phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognition of structures as future material banks. <p>End-of-life phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Voluntary schemes for sustainable buildings may influence the uptake of new approaches for better C&DW. - Urban metabolism supporting circular economy solutions for closing the loops of urbans flows in cities/regions and increasing their regenerative capacity. 	<p>All phases</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Virgin material is considered to have a higher quality than recycled aggregates. - There can be a lack of confidence in the quality/purity of recycled materials.

A careful look of barriers in Table 21 reveals that there are common barriers in all lifecycle phases. The main obstacle for reuse and recycling of wooden products/materials is economic due to often the low price of virgin materials (e.g. wood abundance in Finland) and the processing costs of demolition waste to secure high-quality material for recycling or dismantling cost for reusable products. Other factors hampering recycling relate to variability in the quality of demolition waste, especially its purity if a tight quality control system is not applied. Concerns about the quality (e.g. nails, impurities) and potential presence of hazardous materials, such as paint/glues, lead to a lack of confidence or trust in the recovered waste streams. Many composite elements in the existing building stock cannot be easily recycled because the materials are difficult to separate from each other. The quality of recovered wood from demolition activities varies considerably, which hampers the reuse and recycling of used wood. Wood materials originating from demolition activities are often treated with chemicals and preservatives and typically contain metal fastenings, such as nails and screws. The reuse and recycling of used wood as construction materials is limited by the quality requirements set for construction

materials. For these reasons, wood waste has been primarily used for energy recovery. Other possible uses for wood waste is using clean wood waste as raw material in chip board production or production of wood composites. In summary, development of a quality assurance protocol is therefore crucial for uptake of BASAJAUN products.

Reuse is a clear choice for extending their service life, even if not widely used. Reuse creates many business opportunities in the local communities especially for re-distribution of salvaged materials. In many cases, it is also cheaper to dismantle buildings part-by-part and sell the components than to demolish buildings conventionally and to process the waste. Nevertheless, reuse is not a widespread practice in modern societies. The obstacles of reuse have been documented in the literature and many practical case studies. They include cost, quality, perception and trust among others.

Returning the structural components back to service in the built environment is a rather complex process affecting all the parties involved in the life cycle. Designers have to consider the new source of materials and carefully plan for deconstruction; increased demand for coordination and flexibility in decision making will be needed during construction; and finally, new business areas have to be opened up to provide services for the phase between deconstruction and new construction. The process also depends strongly on the size and complexity of the element or structure that is being reused. In most of the cases, the presented concept competes with other recovery strategies, and therefore, its feasibility has to be always evaluated [93].

Unfortunately, there are many practical obstacles to the reuse of building components that should be addressed. One is the lack of strength grading rules for materials in reused elements. This means that reusable load-bearing components are forced to be applied for non-structural purpose unless they are thoroughly tested. Another example of a barrier is the difficult deconstruction of existing buildings. The extended time and high demands on manual labour is usually thought to increase the cost of the whole process. This can be partly improved by applying standardized deconstruction practices, proper staff training and using selected technologies for deconstruction. A detailed study on technologies, processes and business models for the reuse of structural elements can be found in the final report of the ReUSE project [93].

For design and manufacturing of circular products, it is important that the architect knows how the demolition contractor works, the recycler must know about the technical requirements of the recovered products or materials for reuse and recycling. The recycling process needs to be adapted to provide suitable feedstock for recycling, potentially adding new process steps for material separation. The documentation and access of information on construction products and construction methods is especially important for the demolition and recycling companies. In some cases, the environmental benefits, such as savings in CO₂ emissions, are very case specific, sometimes due to potentially high processing needs in the recovery of waste materials or, in others, to maintenance and rehabilitation activities having environmental impacts. Furthermore, the total environmental impacts of these circular economy solutions depend on the whole or multiple lifecycles of buildings, which can be several decades.

Not only poor or inadequate quality, also the continuity of supply, is a challenge that influence the use of recovered materials in new products. Furthermore, the lack of standards, experience and guidance for ensuring the quality of reusable products hampers reuse. There are also various challenges related to the potential content of hazardous substances, contaminants which are banned today but were acceptable in the past when the products were originally manufactured, that risk being spread in the recycling process. Furthermore, challenges in data transfer along the value chain lower trust in the

quality of recycled/reclaimed materials and products. And for some materials, technological innovations, as well as new business models, are required for more high-grade recycling.

Some of the barriers to certain concepts can be solved by other described concepts in Table 22. Selective demolition, for example, enables high-grade recycling while design for disassembly supports lifetime extension (modular constructions are often easier to renovate), selective demolition and the high-grade recovery of materials. Furthermore, materials passports and systems focused on selective demolition, such as Tracimat, improve the traceability of materials, an important challenge for high-grade recycling. These examples are all connected, and benefits cannot solely be assigned to a specific stage of the value chain.

Table 22 Examples of actions for removing barriers

Life stage	Barriers	Solutions
Design phase	Preferences of architects Lack of knowledge	Standardization Demonstration cases European Green Deal
Manufacturing phase	Lack of national instructions/standards for use of recyclables (CE-marking) Waste status of raw materials Low prices of virgin materials	See above End-of-waste concept Material passports
Construction phase	Conflicts with other legislation (energy efficiency?)	Promotion of reuse Disseamability of products
Use phase	High costs for renovation, material degradation	Use of sensors
End-of-life phase	Complexity of products (products glued) Lack of knowledge of materials	Recycling targets Closed loop requirements

In many cases, the impacts of reuse and recycling are not visible in short term in a better waste management. The introduction of reuse solutions in the design and construction phases that support the prolongation of the lifespan of buildings/components will provide significant environmental benefits in waste management – preventing waste and lowering the amount waste generated. Selective demolition, for example, has an immediate effect on the production of pure fractions for reuse and recycling; prolongation of the lifespan of building products and buildings themselves prevents waste in the short term; and the use of a high content of recyclables in high-grade products avoids downcycling. Other concepts, such as design for disassembly, mainly have an effect during the renovation or demolition of an existing built. The delay, often of several decades, in obtaining measurable circular economy gains in the construction sector may discourage stakeholders from taking action on new material or product management solutions. However, governmental measures can ensure that action that brings long-term environmental benefits is supported economically.

Key conclusions

In all lifecycle phases, the economics of the solutions are the overriding consideration in their uptake. The market acceptance of products produced using waste as an input material will only be assured when production costs are lower than for virgin materials. Besides the economic factors, the quality

of building products and materials is crucial for the uptake of new products. Lack of available documented information on the origins of waste and data on the composition of old construction products can create doubts about quality. Closing the material loops requires new business models and especially communication and commitments between all stakeholders over the entire life cycle.

Standardisation plays an important role in the assessment of the performance of secondary materials in products replacing virgin materials and also in the design of construction products. The challenge in some cases is the scope of the standards and the requirement for CE-marking of construction products covered by harmonised standards.

Several of the R&D projects (ref. EU BASAJAUN, EU HISER; EU ICEBERG; EU IRCOW) on innovative solutions for promoting use of wooden products and materials are financed by EU. These are important for understanding how the circular solutions work beyond a development phase and which factors are critical for upscaling, including information on actual costs. Furthermore, real results from such cases create confidence among stakeholders on new approaches to management of wooden material and products from construction.

ReUSE of wooden products - survey

A detailed survey on the topic was carried out in the project ReUSE by Tampere University of Technology [117]. The futures research method Delphi revealed the experts' opinion about the development of reuse activities in the next decades in Finland. The respondents agreed that even though concrete elements currently have the highest potential for reuse, the potentials of steel and timber may increase significantly in the future. Especially timber CLT panels that have only recently been introduced to the building sector are seen as suitable for future reuse. A major barrier for reusing any materials or components seemed to be the absence of an established deconstruction and reuse practice. A limitation of this study is the fact that the answers represent the opinions of the respondents. The number of respondents was small and the opinions showed a lot of diversity. Therefore, the results are only as valid as the expertise of the surveyed panel.

The greatest impact on the reusability of buildings is in its design stage because most of the obstacles can be reduced already when the new building is planned. Thus, resource efficiency should be considered in designing new building projects [121]. However, design for deconstruction is not a solution for the end of life of the already existing building stock. Therefore, efforts should be made to overcome the barriers of reuse outlined in this paper.

The respondents estimated the percentage of load-carrying components that are likely to be reused by the year 2020 and 2050, and the percentage they would prefer to be reused. The building components used in the survey included columns, wall panels, slabs, beams and trusses made from steel, concrete and wood. The results for 2020 represent the reuse with current practices, which might include some administrative or non-technological changes. The results for 2050 represent reuse potential with significant technological development in building waste recovery and small fraction of the buildings already designed for deconstruction (even though the Finnish industry has not yet taken larger steps towards developing dismantlable building systems).

Table 23 Averages for likely and preferred reuse percentages in Finland in 2020 and 2050 [93]

Material	Components	Likely in 2020 (%)	Preferred in 2020 (%)	Likely in 2050 (%)	Preferred in 2050 (%)
Concrete	Beams	7	15	15	25
	Columns	7	12.5	12.5	20
	Slabs	7	12.5	12.5	25
	Sandwich panels	5	10	10	20
Steel	Beams	7	22.5	20	55
	Columns	7	20	20	50
	Trusses	5	15	20	35
	Sandwich panels	5	17.5	15	35
Timber	Beams	5	20	20	55
	Columns	5	20	20	55
	Trusses	5	10	10	40
	CLT and sandwich panels	5	12.5	20	55

Notes: N.B. The percentages are indicative only. They are only to be used for comparing the different components, materials and scenarios.

The results of the survey (Table 23) show that steel and concrete columns and beams have the best reuse potential with current building and demolition practices. However, after implementing new technologies, steel and timber elements are more likely to be reused than concrete according to the respondents' opinion. Steel and timber beams and columns are also the most preferred elements for reuse. The most significant difference is between sandwich panels from the selected materials. The preference of timber sandwich or CLT panels reuse in 2050 is more than double of the concrete ones. The percentages in Table 23 should not be taken as exact predictions but used for comparing the different scenarios. In addition, it should be noted that the results have to be interpreted in connection with the real material volumes in demolished buildings (Meinander and Mroueh, 2012) [123] and their location (Huuhka and Lahdensivu, 2014) [122]. For example, steel buildings, which the panel associated with relatively high reuse potential, are only a small minority in the Finnish building stock.

The panellists were also asked to evaluate the barriers for reusing the aforementioned components component-by-component and material-by-material. The absence of established practices (which consists of lacks of demand, supply, awareness, applications and examples as well as market-related issues such as difficulty of scheduling, cost and attractiveness of conventional recycling) seemed to be the main barrier for reusing concrete and steel components in general. Technological constraints were also seen to affect some steel and concrete elements, while timber components were seen to be challenged by the nature of timber as a biodegradable material (damage and health risks).

9 Good practices of material circularity

9.1 Material passports

EU BAMB project² [124] developed Electronic Material Passports by giving a place for material information. This information describing pre-defined characteristics of materials in products that give them value for recovery and reuse. BAMB listed many benefits, which is achieved by this system, and when the information is accessible for different stakeholders, at their specific information need stage:

- Increase the value or keep the value of materials, products and components over time;
- Create incentives for suppliers to produce healthy, sustainable and circular materials/building products;
- Support materials choices in Reversible Building Design projects;
- Make it easier for developers, managers and renovators to choose healthy, sustainable and circular building materials;
- Facilitate reversed logistics and take back of products, materials and components.

Figure 37 C2C Biological and technical cycles for the Circular Economy [124]

² <https://www.bamb2020.eu/topics/materials-passports/>

For the beneficial utilization of waste materials, material passports should be existing. These passports should include all relevant information for reuse of material and recycle of material substance. This would be possible through the construction industry digitalization. Digitalisation is the key to managing information throughout the life cycle of products and thus forms the basis for the efficient utilization of once used materials.

Material passports are closely linked to the Building Information Models (BIM). From BIMs building designer could get information from materials to include it into the design or report about the materials, which could not be used for re-design.

Material passport idea should be widened to cover also data from the use phase until end of life and beyond. Understanding material history from acquisition, product production, use, maintenance, and deconstruction allows us to make the decisions for better utilization of wooden material substance, rather to utilize it for the energy production.

9.2 Design for disassembly and reuse/recycling

At the level of design there are two primary ways to assure a recyclable and/or reusable construction. First, and as has most likely been covered already in these pages, selection of materials suitable for recycling is the baseline for a sustainable product. Secondly, and most uniquely for construction, is designing for disassembly. Often, and because of the high standards of enclosure and safety required, buildings are explicitly built not to be taken apart under any circumstance. The idea of disassembly runs against the concept of weatherproofing, one of the basic principles of building technology developed in the modern era. Particularly with metals, glass, and plastics they have been welded, fused, and glued to make them safer, tighter, and (literally and figuratively) cleaner. Adhesives, connections, and techniques are being developed to make those materials easier to disassemble, but timber-based construction is inherently easier to disassemble. Wood components are almost always connected mechanically, whether it's with nails, screws, bolts, or plate connectors. Of course, some structural products include adhesives, so we should think about simple recycling and reuse to understand how each component type and product should be considered. In this way, **design for disassembly has an additional prerequisite for better material utilization, as contaminants in demolished wood are minimal.**

If introduced at the project definition phase, the concepts for design for disassembly can be used to reduce and/or prevent waste and increase resource efficiency by encouraging alternative considerations. In this phase primary decisions about material types and building structures are made that will have an impact on the rest of building design process and service life. The application of adaptability concepts and principles can minimize the need for unnecessary demolition and new construction, by repurposing or modifying built assets to renew their service life and result in built assets that are able to accommodate a broader variety of uses.

Design for Downcycling or Upcycling

Looking at the product from the outside in we know that in order to be recycled they must, at minimum, be clean, not contain conflicting or contaminated materials, and individual materials must be able to be separated.

When this is not satisfactorily achieved, to return the product materials close to their virgin state, then the materials will be at best be downcycled. This most likely involves a less expensive and more readily available process for retrieval. From a design perspective, this is not optimal but may bring about some creative innovative solutions for other product types. Usually these uses would not be meant for direct consumer use, but volume may have a positive effect on the reuse or recycling of a product. Creating pulp is an easy disposal of any wood product, and that pulp can be used in paper and back in a building as insulation. It could also be used, when material strength is not a safety issue, as fill in bio-composites and bioplastics. And, although ending the life cycle, wood waste can also be used as biofuel.

When materials can be extracted in a cleaner manner, then it is possible to put them back into use with a higher market value or as primary product material. Upcycling should be the goal of all materials that have been combined into products. Continuing to use a material in its original state (ie. not as filler or in any way chemically bonded or recomposed) is a way of upcycling and extend its life cycle. Particularly within the same industry, reusing waste materials as storage or packaging. And, if a mostly singular material can be used (and reused), insulation also becomes upcycling.

The unique position of the building industry is the wide range of aesthetic finishes that are required in the completion of a building. This could be anything from carpet or other floor finishes to wall papers or textiles. One only needs to look at the renaissance of cork as a sustainable finishing material to understand how other bio-based materials could be used to add a specific aesthetic and comfort while increasing the overall sustainability of a building. When strength and durability are not primary criteria wood waste products can be used in creative and novel ways to improve the look and feel of buildings and spaces. These uses are effective in two ways. Firstly, by giving greater value to the waste material. Secondly, and perhaps more important, is that their use brings awareness to the public of efforts of designers, architects, clients and contractors to create the most sustainable environment possible.

Design for Reuse

Creating products for reuse is a much more complex design problem than preparing for recycling. Enabling a product to be reused will have a greater effect on the assembly and aesthetic (form, finish, and details) of a product. From this standpoint, the criteria for reuse are stricter for a designer than those for recycling.

The basics of reuse, as with recycling, starts with material selection. In the case of reuse, the material itself must have an applicable extension of its life cycle. There is no such thing as 'down-use'. Reuse is by definition across or up the value chain. So, the connection methods used have an even greater effect on reusability than recyclability. As mentioned in the introduction, there are two basic connection types: wet and dry. A wet connection means one that uses adhesives or glues. This type is not preferred unless the adhesive is easily soluble, and that method can be included in the disassembly process. A dry connection means one that is mechanically connected. A mechanical connection could be screwed, bolted, nailed, custom connected, or made with a wood joint. Dry connections will always be preferred when designing for reuse. Furthermore, the more accessible the joint the easier it will be to disconnect when disassembling. The difficulty as a designer at this point is assuring structural integrity, mechanical functioning, and an aesthetic quality that meets the expectation of you and your client. A designer is always juggling these aspects of a project, and designing for reuse adds an additional, constraining layer. This, of course, can also bring opportunities.

Design for reuse, once materials have been chosen, is very much about design for disassembly. In order to understand how to design for the process of disassembly, it's best to work backwards from site to factory and back out the front door of the factory. As discussed above, mechanical connections should be used to fix components on site. In this context larger modular components are best suited for disassembly. In addition to the increased efficiency of installation/de-installation, modular components would be disassembled off-site in a warehouse or factory (as they were originally assembled), which enables more careful disassembly and sorting of components.

Two concepts are important to consider in this step: functional decomposition and component hierarchy. These are separate but intertwined concepts. Functional decomposition refers the integration, but separation of functions (structure, electrical, plumbing, finishes, etc.) with a module. When designing for efficiency and modularity the design usually strives for the most integration possible. In the case of designing for reuse, the integration of systems cannot be considered without allowing for space (literally or figuratively) for disassembling the components of those systems within the module. An understanding of the component hierarchy in our module is related to its functional decomposition in that the excessive interrelation and interconnection of components will not allow for their decomposition. The simplest component hierarchy is the best solution. For instance, maintaining one spine or structural component onto which all sub-systems are attached will be the best kind of hierarchy. When interconnection is necessary, maintain a clear sequence of attachment from one component to the next without bundling 3 or more systems into one. The small amount of efficiency gained will likely negatively impact the disassembly process.

Finally, when the components or full modules are disassembled and reused there are likely to be small damages in the product. Repair should also be designed and planned for. A designer can consider this when selecting materials and their adjacencies, and when designing the connections for access. Ideas like sacrificial panels or easily patched materials can assist this. Some 'remanufacturing' is also likely to occur. Some components could also be repurposed, like upcycling. Though, this is a more difficult strategy to design for, and material selection is more likely to impact this aspect.

In complex building projects, one system is often not the most efficient for solving main structure facades, walls, floors, et al. Hybrid prefab buildings (i.e. combining concrete with wood-based modules) can be effective, and still allow for easy recycling and reuse. In this case the rules for disassembly and recycling above still apply, but some care should be taken on site to assure the most effective installation and de-installation.

Solutions

Some solutions have already been described above, but others remain to be imagined and implemented. Firstly, and as alluded to above, the shape of components and modules at the macro and micro level can assist in de-installation and disassembly. This could be the curvature and size limits of a wall, the type of reveal between components, or the design of an access panel. The second, and still speculative, approach is to search for new technologies that can assist engineers and designers in their work. Much of the disassembly process is a functional decomposition optimization exercise. The kind of process that can be improved with the machine learning type of artificial intelligence. Most industrial timber and prefabrication processes are digitally driven, so the base data is available to begin a machine learning process. The iterations possible through computation are exponentially greater than what is possible with designers and engineers. The value will come from increased efficiency and more possibilities for recycling and even greater possibilities for reuse.

There is a great deal of momentum for circularity in the design world now. It is still seen as too expensive, because the capital cost will be higher while the value is not yet able to be fully quantified. We are still asking designers, engineers, and owners to take a risk that the process will continue as projected. Any strategy that can support that process will be valuable. This should happen all along the development value chain, from owners, to contractors, to designers, to computational processes.

International Standard about principles, requirements and guidance for the Design for disassembly and adaptability (DfD/A) is released in 2020 [125]. Different actors, especially designers, should consider DfD principles, because in case when DfD is not taken into account in design phase, building renovations or demolitions projects are not be able easily salvage materials for reuse and recycling. Therefore, those processes producing waste which is then landfilled or incinerated.

Figure 38 Target groups and specific objectives (Design for circularity) [126].

Construction solution for circular economy:

- "Urban Mining" and reverse cycles, which promote the circular economy of building materials to be demolished and used in new construction sites
- extension of life cycles through the conversion and refurbishment of buildings, where buildings that are still usable are converted to new uses and their value is increased by renovating them, while the materials remain in use for longer;
- design of new buildings for demolition and re-use and flexible construction, creating flexible circular construction solutions in new projects so that the buildings can be easily dismantled, and parts re-used.

10 Discussion and Recommendations

Wood used for construction includes wide range of products. Structural and engineered products are among highest value products from wood. Sawn timber added value obtained directly in the sawmill which represents only the ~50% of the tree, the rest are by-products with a lower value. Production of wooden materials generates wastes and by-products, which should not be wasted.

During the building life cycle, wooden waste generates also from installation, refurbishment and after the building end of life, through the demolition process. Wooden waste and by-products have a huge potential for material recycling into a new product, which could rise their value over the incineration and energy utilization. Beneficial is to keep wooden product in circulation to avoid release of stored carbon as long as possible.

Wooden material reuse and recycling having a positive effect to all three-sustainability performance aspects (environment protection, economic- and social advantages).

- *Environment protection:* reduce extraction of natural resources, reduce wooden waste generation, extends carbon storage from first used product to the second and third transformation, reduce carbon footprint of buildings.
- *Economic advantages:* reduce payments for landfill and disposal, reduce construction industry cost.
- *Social advantages:* general awareness of efficient use of recycled materials creates new possibility for the secondary material business value chain (from building demolition to material recovery and utilization by recycling scheme into new products).

From an economic point of view, it is essential that the delay between the generation of the wood waste and its recycling or recovery is as short as possible. This is even more pronounced for wood waste than, for example, concrete waste. If the delay is long, proper storage is needed to avoid quality deteriorating. This may rise the cost and reduce competitiveness of wood waste.

According to Eurostat, the production of construction wood waste is concentrated in a small number of EU member states. The reason for this is either the small market share of wood products (no waste is therefore generated) or virgin wood is well available and widely used. The latter are the Nordic countries, where due to the long heating season; waste wood is used for heating.

Due to the preference for timber-framed buildings, pure wood waste is available in Finland, while in Germany and Spain wood waste is more typically treated and processed wood. While wood waste streams differ from each other, also the further utilization possibilities are different.

BASAJAUN project creates strategies of resource optimization to foster the best use of wood and wooden waste by developing innovative wood-based construction materials and construction systems (façade, interior partitions, roofs and structural elements) and by upscale the manufacture of high-quality wood-based products. It is shown than using wood waste as a source for foam formed insulation slight benefit according to GWP could achieved, but more beneficial is that carbon stored in wooden substance will extend through waste transformation into the next product.

There is no 'one' good advice than other exists, to reach zero waste production in wood construction. Zero-waste strategy in the wood construction sector could be achieved in collaboration and with the effort of all construction sector value chain.

Main recommendations of this study

1. Prevention of wood waste is the priority for the zero-waste strategy in wood construction, but it is not the only possibility.
2. Developed new products with recycled content should be also reusable or recyclable, after end of their first life.
3. Utilization of wooden by-products and offcuts are safe way to use wooden substance with upgrading their value
4. Utilization of wooden substance from wooden products through second or even third transformation for the new products avoids waste generation.
5. Development of EoW criteria for wood products to change the waste status to product status support the uptake of recycled materials
6. Securing high quality of wood materials/products is crucial for their market uptake after deconstruction and demolition. This requires maintenance, monitoring and adequate separation methods of the materials collected for recycling.
7. Important is also to recognize hazardous substances that are regulated and banned from recycling. Such materials might appear in the wooden waste and hamper the use of developed products.
8. Development of material passports and traceability concept to create trust for end-users for the new wooden products
9. Development of harmonized standards to enable CE-marking of recycled wooden products.
10. The manufacturers of new products from recycled materials should provide the tools for clear definition of recyclability criteria for such materials (requirements for waste quality and separation should be set). The guidance can be for instance developed in the industrial associations.
11. Create structural solutions and connections suitable for material deconstruction and reuse
12. Assessment of zero waste status should be based on the whole life of the building and cannot be limited only to waste originating from and used by construction industry.

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Basajaun is a European innovation action about sustainable building with wood. The main objective is to demonstrate how wood construction chains can be optimized to foster both rural development and urban transformation whilst being connected with sustainable forest management in Europe. The consortium comprises 29 partners from 12 countries including 8 leading research and technology organizations, 3 universities, 15 companies and 4 other public and sectoral organizations. The project is coordinated by the Tecnalia Research and Innovation Foundation in Spain

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